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A spatial valuation approach of timber provisioning in Finnish forests

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Forest Information Technology

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Streszczenie

Oprócz stworzenia mapy ekosystemów oraz oszacowania ich stanu oraz ich usług do roku 2014 Strategia Bioróżnorodności EU2020 również zobowiązała kraje członkowskie do określenia ekonomicznej wartości ich usług do 2020 roku. Ekosystemy dają różne materialne i nie materialne korzyści dla ludzi. Niestety te często bardzo ważne korzyści są często ignorowane ponieważ nie można ich wartości zmierzyć w pieniądzu i nie są postrzegane jako towar. Drewno wszelako jest dobrem namacalnym oraz może być nabyte na rynku za określoną cenę. W fińskich lasach przeprowadzono studium przypadku w celu wykazania potrzeby wyceny przestrzennej w zaopatrzeniu w drewno. Podejście bazowane na GIS, używające dokładnej inwentaryzacji lasów w celu oszacowania aktualnej wartości fińskich lasów i równego ekwiwalentu rocznego oraz umieszczenia ich na mapie w rozdzielczości przestrzennej 100 metrów na 100 metrów. Wzrost lasów był szacowany na 3 sposoby: modelowanie regionalnej wydajności, użycie inwentaryzacyjnej bazy danych EFISCEN oraz symulatora MOTTI. Używając domyślnych wytycznych MOTTI wybrano 4 główne grupy gatunków do oceny spośród 16 lokalizacji. Przy stopie procentowej w wysokości 1%, aktualna wartość netto lasu sosnowego sięga maksymalnie 8,920 za hektar z roczną równowartością 243 € za ha za rok. Za las świerkowy maksymalna wartość to 12,355 € za hektar z roczną równowartością 293 € za hektar za rok. Brzoza oraz inne szerokolistne gatunki są mniej dochodowe. Przy stopie procentowej w wysokości 5% większość lasów była niedochodowa oprócz niektórych lasów sosnowych i świerkowych rosnących na żyznych mineralnych południowych glebach. To studium nie sugeruje, że lasy mniej dochodowe lub niedochodowe nie są cenne. Rezultaty sugerują, że wybór obu metod szacowania wydajności i scenariuszy zarządzania może mieć wyraźny wpływ na rentowność, szczególnie na terenach z obniżoną stopą procentową oraz na żyznych glebach.

Słowa kluczowe: przestrzenna wycena wartości, aktualna wartość netto, równy ekwiwalent roczny, mapa rentowności lasów, usługi ekosystemów, modelowanie wielkości wzrostu, funkcje dochodu.

Abstract

The EU 2020 Biodiversity Strategy, in addition to mapping and assessing the state of ecosystems and their services by 2014, also required the Member States to assess the economic value of such services by 2020. Forest ecosystems provide several tangible and intangible benefits to humankind. Unfortunately, such vital benefits are usually ignored by policy makers since they lack monetary value and are not perceived as commodities. However, wood is usually a tangible good that can be bought in markets for a certain price. A case study was conducted across Finnish forests in order to address the need of spatially valuating timber provisioning. A GIS based approach making use of detailed national forest inventory data was explored for estimating and mapping the net present values of Finnish forests and their equal annual equivalent at 100×100 m spatial resolution. Forest growth was approximated in three ways: with yield functions, using the EFISCEN inventory database and the MOTTI forest stands simulator. Given the default MOTTI management guidelines, four main groups of species within sixteen different site conditions were considered for appraisal. At a discount rate of one per cent, the net present value of pine forest stands reached a maximum of 8,920 € ha⁻¹ with an annual equivalent of 243 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹. For the spruce stands, the maximum net present value was 12,355 € ha⁻¹ with an annual equivalent of 293 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹. Birch and other broad-leaved species were less profitable. At a discount rate of five per cent, most of the forests were unprofitable except for certain pine and spruce stands on fertile southern mineral soils. However, this study does not suggest that less profitable or unprofitable forest stands are not valuable. The results indicate that the choice of both the yield estimation method and the management scenario can significantly impact profitability predictions, particularly at low discount rates and on fertile sites.

Key words: timber spatial valuation, net present value, equal annual equivalent, forest profitability map, ecosystem services, forest growth modelling, yield functions

Zusammenfassung

Die Biodiversitätsstrategie der Europäischen Union bis 2020 sieht vor, dass alle EU-Mitgliedsstaaten bis 2014 den Zustand ihrer Ökosysteme und die von ihnen erbrachten Dienstleistungen kartieren und beurteilen sollen. Darüber hinaus soll bis 2020 der ökonomische Wert dieser Dienstleistungen geschätzt werden. Waldökosysteme sind für Menschen sowohl materiell als auch immateriell von Nutzen. Leider werden wesentliche Funktionen von Entscheidungsträgern meist ignoriert, wenn sich ihr Wert nicht finanziell beziffern lässt und sie nicht als Güter wahrgenommen werden. Demgegenüber stellt Holz ein materielles Gut dar, das auf Märkten zu einem gewissen Preis gehandelt werden kann. In finnischen Wäldern wurde eine Fallstudie zum Zwecke der räumlichen Bewertung der Holzbestände durchgeführt. Ein GIS-basierter Ansatz in Kombination mit detaillierten Daten der nationalen Forstinventur wurde erforscht, um den Kapitalwert finnischer Wälder und den entsprechenden jährlichen Gegenwert mit einer räumlichen Auflösung von 100 m mal 100 m zu schätzen und zu kartieren. Das Waldwachstum wurde auf drei Weisen angenähert: durch Modellierung regionaler Ertragsfunktionen, mittels der EFISCEN Inventurdatenbank und mit dem MOTTI Waldbestandssimulator. Unter den gegebenen Standard-Management-Richtlinien von MOTTI wurden vier Hauptartengruppen innerhalb von sechzehn unterschiedlichen Standortbedingungen für die Schätzung berücksichtigt. Bei einer Zinsrate von einem Prozent erreichte der Kapitalwert von Kiefernbeständen ein Maximum von 8920 € ha⁻¹ mit einem jährlichen Gegenwert von 243 € ha⁻¹ Jahr⁻¹. Für Fichtenbestände lag der maximale Kapitalwert bei 12355 € ha⁻¹ mit einem jährlichen Gegenwert von 293 € ha⁻¹ Jahr⁻¹. Birken und andere Laubgehölzarten waren weniger profitabel. Bei einer Zinsrate von fünf Prozent waren die meisten Wälder unprofitabel, mit Ausnahme einiger Kiefern- und Fichtenbestände auf fruchtbaren Mineralböden im Süden. Die Ergebnisse dieser Studie bedeuten jedoch keinesfalls, dass weniger profitable oder unprofitable Waldbestände wertlos sind. Die Studie weist darauf hin, dass die Wahl der Ertragsschätzmethode und des Managementszenarios entscheidenden Einfluss auf die Profitabilität haben, besonders bei niedrigen Zinsraten und fruchtbaren Böden.

Schlüsselwörter: räumliche Holzwertschätzung, Kapitalwert, jährlicher Gegenwert, Waldprofitabilitätskarte, Ökosystemdienstleistungen, Waldwachstumsmodellierung, Ertragsfunktionen

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List of abbreviations

EAE	Equal Annual Equivalent
ESS	Ecosystem Services
EU	European Union
EVRI	Environmental Valuation Reference Inventory
FESS	Forest Ecosystem Services
FSA	Forest Stand Address
LEV	Land Expectation Value
MS-NFI	Multi-source National Forest Inventory Raster Maps
NPV	Net Present Value
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics

1. Introduction

1.1. Context and motivation for the study

1.1.1. The need for valuating forest ecosystem services

The need for valuating forest ecosystem services (FESS) is rooted in the more general need for valuating ecosystem services (ESS), which gained high interest in the contemporary ecosystem services science. Moreover, valuating ESS represents interest for various institutions like the Conservation International or the World Bank (Matulis 2014). Likewise, the Nature Conservancy, the World Bank and the World Conservation Union expressed their interest in valuating ESS and assessing the economic value of conservation (Pagiola et al. 2004). A boost in the science of ESS valuation was also generated by the studies of the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment in 2005 (Crossman et al 2012). *Considering this general context, the present study tackles the valuation of FESS.*

Navrud & Pruckner (1997) pointed out that valuating the environment in the 1960s and 1970s was mainly carried in U.S.A. and also gained importance in Europe in the 1980s and 1990s. However, they emphasize that in Europe fewer valuation studies were used as supportive tools in the process of environmental decision-making. In Europe, according to Action 5 of the EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2020, the Member States were called upon to map and assess the state of ecosystems and their services by 2014 and also to assess the economic value of such services by 2020 (Maes et al. 2014). The Working Group on Mapping and Assessment on Ecosystems and their Services, which was mandated to coordinate and oversee Action 5, developed a typology for ecosystems in Europe and pointed out four main ecosystem types: agro-ecosystems, forest ecosystems, freshwater ecosystems and marine ecosystems (Maes et al. 2013). Furthermore, FESS are structured in three main sections, that is, provisioning, regulating/maintenance and cultural. The provisioning section includes forest production of biomass (e.g. timber, pulp wood, fuel wood), water and energy (Maes et al. 2014). *In a more specific context, the present thesis focuses on economic valuation and mapping the economic value of timber production.*

Production of timber can be perceived as a flow of raw material from forest ecosystems which, combined with manufacturing and human capital services, produces human welfare (*sensu* Costanza et al. 1997). Nevertheless, enhancing human welfare has to be done in a sustainable way, in a win-win manner for both human activities and the environment. Therefore, valuating our ecosystems can turn out to be a useful guide (Farber et al. 2002).

The complexity of ecological systems (e.g. forest ecosystems) and their services (e.g. ground water for drinking, plants, wild animals, timber) presents difficulties for our ability to place a monetary value on their benefits (Fisher et al. 2009). However, timber is usually perceived as an ecosystem good that can be bought in markets for a certain price (Häyhä & Franzese 2014). Therefore, contrasting the price volatility of non-timber services, the relative ease of setting stumpage prices for different wood assortments (e.g. sawlogs, pulpwood) allows for a more detailed valuation of standing timber. This value can be considered as the opportunity cost of protecting certain sites, a practice also used by governments for land acquisition, where the value of standing timber represents compensation payments (Juutinen et al. 2008). However, this compensation practice is not without fault. The Economist criticized that this practice can undervalue forests, leading to uncontrolled logging (Astill 2010).

Last but not least, in the forestry sector, as in any economically driven sector, an important objective is to maximize profit. Profitability is measured with benefits and costs. Valuating the benefits and knowing the costs are therefore necessary informational steps. Also, appraising the desirability of a given management scheme is done by comparing benefits and costs. The analysis of costs and benefits can also help determine investment priorities (Snowdon & Harou 2013). Furthermore, in the process of analysing how policies contribute to sustainable development, it is important to identify the economic, social and environmental impacts of the respective policies, and thinking in terms of costs and benefits strengthen the analysis (European Commission 2009). *Particularly, the present thesis tackles the estimation of benefits and usage of known costs in order to model and map forest stand profitability.*

1.1.2. The need for mapping the value of forest ecosystem services

Mapping the value of ecosystem goods and services is justified by the fact that these values are characterized by an intrinsic spatial nature. That is, the supply and demand for such values are spatially explicit (Troy & Wilson 2006; Crossman et al. 2013) and the value of standing timber is no exception. Furthermore, such maps capture important spatial information that can be used for communication and decision-making (Crossman et al. 2013). Mapping the value of standing timber can help with estimating the opportunity cost of sites and with designating potential conservation areas. For instance, in a Finnish case study, Juutinen et al. (2008) included site economic value as an important factor in their selection model for protected areas in boreal forest. Likewise, mapping the value of timber can also be useful for predicting logging movements and therefore road developments, which can be further used for estimating the spatial patterns of deforestation (Ahmed & Ewers 2012). Moreover, having spatially explicit monetary values of forest may help agricultural and forest policymakers in the context of land-use change implications (Yemshanov et al. 2007). Last but not least, maps are an important communication tool and they have ‘an air of authority’ (Hauck et al. 2013). In this regard they can be used as a tool for raising awareness about the value of our forests and their services because only when society learns how to properly value nature does society adequately protect nature (Matulis 2014).

1.2. Literature review and concepts related to valuation and profitability

Conducting an ISI Web of Science search through 2007 while using the term ‘ecosystem services’ or ‘ecological services’, Fisher et al. (2009) showed that the number of papers tackling ESS rose exponentially. Thus, the authors underlined the growing research trend and popularity of ESS studies. Moreover, several recent literature reviews showed that mapping such services, including FESS, also gained high interest in ESS contemporary science (e.g. Egoh et al. 2012; Martínez-Harms & Balvanera 2012; Crossman et al. 2012; Schägner et al. 2013; Häyhä & Franzese 2014; Pagella & Sinclair 2014).

Mapping the monetary value of a service (e.g. economic value of the growing stock, €/ha) or the specific biophysical metrics characterizing that service (e.g. growing stock, m³/ha) are the two main ways implied in ESS mapping (Schägner et al. 2013;

Häyhä & Franzese 2014). However, the economic value of an ecosystem service is more informative for policy makers (Häyhä et al. 2015).

Several studies have already dealt with mapping the economic value of FESS, using benefit transfer as a valuation method (e.g. Troy & Wilson 2006; Elsasser et al. 2009; Liu 2010b; Carrasco et al. 2014; Frélichová et al. 2014). Specialized online databases have already been developed for ESS valuation, which can include studies that also mapped the economic values of FESS. For example, currently, the Canadian EVRI¹ database (de Civita et al. 2011) offers almost one thousand studies when queried for the word 'forest'. The number of studies is reduced to less than one hundred when the key words combination 'map AND forest' is used. One major drawback of this database is the fact that is accessible only to researchers from the United Kingdom and France (Elsasser et al. 2009). Another example is given by Carrasco et al. (2014); they use The Economics of Biodiversity and Ecosystems dataset (Van der Ploeg & De Groot 2010; de Groot et al. 2012) to map the total ESS values of tropical forests. Schägner et al. (2013) mentioned the UK NEA (UK NEA 2014) as a promising initiative in ESS value mapping, which includes maps of the value of timber across the United Kingdom. Furthermore, a compilation of valuation databases is provided by The Ecosystem Services Partnership (ESP 2014). Nevertheless, they are not focused solely on FESS studies and therefore specific searches are needed.

However, a comprehensive and up to date review on mapping the economic value of ESS (FESS included) was found to be the one of Schägner et al. (2013). They found only 69 studies on mapping the economic value of ESS of which a quarter were focused on forest ecosystems with 8 tackling timber provision. It seems that there is no review tackling solely the mapping of the economic values of FESS. Nevertheless, Ninan & Inoue (2013) presented a review on studies concerned solely with estimating the value of FESS, although no mapping approach was reviewed. Another relatively recent review, Barrio & Loureiro (2010), focused solely on forest values but without considering economic valuation mapping methods.

¹ Environmental Valuation Reference Inventory

Valuating FESS is no different from the valuation approaches used for ESS in general. There are many ways of valuating ecosystem services and their applicability is mostly context related (La Notte et al. 2012). For further details, in a review covering the research development of ESS valuation, Liu 2010a summarized several non-monetizing and monetary valuation methods used in ESS valuation. However, 'countries are free to choose the methods best suited for valuing their forest assets' (Eurostat 2000).

This study is limited to valuating wood growing stock per hectare. Such valuation falls into market methods because wood is commonly perceived as an ecosystem good that can be bought in markets (Fisher et al. 2009). Furthermore, stumpage prices are recommended to be used for the valuation of standing timber (Eurostat 2000).

After investigating the literature, two main monetary valuation methods were identified for the timber provision of cultivated forests: *stumpage value* and *net present value* (NPV). These monetary valuation methods are further discussed in the next section with corresponding literature references. The NPV also represents a form of estimating the profitability of forest investments (Soucy & Kershaw 2010). The NPV method is further used in this study.

1.2.1. Stumpage and consumption value

At a given time along the management cycle of a forest stand, the growing stock (m^3/ha) has a certain stumpage value based on the current market prices for different assortments that can be harvested. The Eurostat pilot programme in forest accounting specified that the stumpage value can be calculated by multiplying the total growing stock (m^3/ha) with an average stumpage price or by multiplying the growing stock per species with the average stumpage prices of corresponding species (Eurostat 2000). The consumption value method can be seen as a more detailed variant of the stumpage value method because the timber is categorized in terms of species and age or diameter classes with corresponding stumpage prices (Eurostat 2000).

The stumpage value is a simple method and has been embraced by many authors. For example, in Finland, Juutinen et al. (2008) considered that the stumpage value of growing stock located on a given site can be used to estimate the opportunity costs of

protecting that particular site. Merry et al. (2009) and Ahmed & Ewers (2012) applied the stumpage value method when estimating the monetary value of standing timber across the Amazon. When mapping the direct use value of forests located in Zhejiang province of southeast China, Chen et al. (2009) applied a slightly different approach by deciding to multiply the stumpage prices with the net annual volume-increments. Certain authors felt the need to introduce harvesting costs in their economic estimations. For example, Grêt-Regamey et al. (2008), when estimating the value of wood production in a district in the Swiss Alps, mentioned that timber production was not profitable given the harvesting costs. In this first study they didn't include such costs but later on the same area was considered for further investigation and the harvesting costs were included (Grêt-Regamey et al. 2013).

Remaining within the context of multiplying a quantity with a price, a different valuation approach was used by Li et al. (2006) to map the monetary value of the annual production of organic matter in the Qinba mountains of Shaanxi Province of China. They argued that the value of organic matter can be calculated by multiplying the dry weight of organic matter with the market price of standard coal.

However, valuating growing stock by multiplying with the corresponding local market prices does not consider the expected growth of forest nor the land value. On the other hand, these two factors could be neglected for mature forests (Juutinen et al. 2008). Moreover, the European System of Accounts recommends separating forest land from timber values by suggesting that the value of forest land should be best assessed through market prices only (Eurostat 2000).

Both the stumpage value and consumption value methods can be considered as simplified versions of the net present value approach with the strong assumption that the discount rate is identical with the growth rate of the forest (Eurostat 2000; Lange 2004). The complexity of the net present value method is that it considers forest growth.

1.2.2. Profitability indices: the net present value (NPV) and its equal annual equivalent (EAE)

Effectively, timber continues to grow with a certain rate until the moment of final cut. This natural growth accrues to the initial stumpage value creating future benefits and their present value has to be taken into account, justifying the use of present value methods as recommended by the Eurostat pilot programme in forest accounting (Eurostat 2000). Computing the net present value (NPV) of a forest based on estimated cash flows is regarded as 'probably the most common method currently used for assessing forest estate value' (Holopainen et al. 2010). The NPV approach is in accordance with Faustmann's theory that the real value of timber is given by the discounted future stumpage value of mature timber after subtracting the costs that occurred during reaching maturity (Eurostat 2000; Lange 2004). Additionally, the NPV is also one of the main profitability indicators of the cost-benefit analysis used in assessing and comparing competing investment projects (Prokofieva & Thorsen 2011; Snowdon & Harou 2013). Also, the annualized form of the NPV, the equal annual equivalent (EAE), can be used in the same manner (e.g. Hynynen et al. 2005; Olssen et al. 2012). The EAE brings the advantage of evaluating investments with different time spans (Prokofieva & Thorsen 2011).

Illustrating the meaning of discounting, Prokofieva & Thorsen (2011) argue that an individual will prefer receiving a certain amount of money today rather than in the future. Thus, a high discount rate indicates a higher preference to the present consumption of a given amount of money. Related to the time span of environmental investments, high discount rates imply a low importance of long-term investments, that is, preference for immediate benefits (Yi, Wong, et al. 2014).

Even though the NPV method was recommended by Eurostat, this approach is regarded as being rather cumbersome because it requires precise knowledge of the cash flows, that is, knowing the exact benefits and costs and at what time they occur during the management cycle of a forest stand (Eurostat 2000; Lange 2004). Furthermore, predicting benefits requires information concerning forest growth (e.g. yield tables,

curves or equations²). A severe limitation is that this kind of information is not always available. Moreover, results of the Eurostat pilot programme in forest accounting showed that the stumpage value method (presented in the previous section) is more suitable for international comparisons because of higher data availability for its calculation (Eurostat 2000). Nevertheless, with all its drawbacks regarding data availability, the NPV approach still remains a sound way of valuating forests (Eurostat 2000; Holopainen et al. 2010).

One of the pioneer studies in mapping timber NPV is the Ph.D. thesis of Bateman (1996). The author first estimated yield class models for Sitka spruce and beech in Wales, United Kingdom based on several environmental variables and then he produced yield class maps. In parallel, he developed tables of NPVs across various yield classes for the two species at various discount rates. Next, he connected the yield class maps with the corresponding NPVs. One of the most recent studies concerned with modelling and mapping NPV is from Yi, Cannon, et al. (2014) who mapped the NPV of rubber plantations in southwest China. Their methodology is similar to the one developed by Bateman (1996).

Yemshanov et al. (2007) mapped NPVs for red pine, Norway spruce and black walnut in southern Ontario, Canada and assessed the economic feasibility of the species. The authors used site index maps and corresponding growth and yield models combined with information regarding the intensity of silvicultural management. The authors stressed the high demand of data not only for wood prices and management costs but also for growth and yield estimates.

Chan et al. (2011) mapped the economic values for harvestable timber, carbon storage and recreational angling in the Central Interior of British Columbia. Instead of using or computing growth and yield models, they used timber supply reviews for estimating the volume of harvestable timber. The authors also underlined the difficulties of data availability. They discussed the bias that might arise by using timber supply reviews instead of modelling the growth of the forest stands.

² The yield tables, curves or equations predict the total volume production attained at a specified age.

Polasky et al. (2011), among other objectives of their study, also used a detailed dataset to compute NPVs for Douglas fir stands of the Willamette Basin in Oregon, USA. The authors had access to information regarding yield for each site index at desired forest stand ages. The net price of timber was modelled based on logging and hauling costs.

Computing and mapping a form of NPV without costs was done by Ojea et al. (2012) for the Spanish Mediterranean region. They also did not consider yield functions but used data from the national forest inventory. The authors underlined that the desire to differentiate stumpage prices between age classes, management regimes, spatial locations, or assortments was hindered by scarcity and lack of reliable data.

Using a map of the Atlantic forests of Paraguay, Naidoo & Ricketts (2006) estimated and mapped the NPV of five different ecosystem services: bushmeat, timber, bio-prospecting ('value for new pharmaceutical products'), existence value, and carbon storage. The authors assumed a 30 years harvest cycle with a harvest rate of four trees per hectare. Using other studies, they constructed estimates for an average per-tree value.

Many other studies tackled solely the computation of NPV or the Faustmann's land expectation value (LEV) without considering the spatial variation of these profitability indicators. The difference between LEV and NPV is that in computing LEV all future rotations of timber are included, while in the case of NPV only one rotation is considered (Straka 2007). For example, using a forest growth simulator, Hanewinkel et al. (2010) deducted the cash flows for Norway spruce and European beech stands of Baden-Württemberg. They computed LEV using the net stumpage value at the end of the rotation time, the net revenue for thinning and the cost for replanting. The strength of their study is the complex analysis of the sensitivity of results by changing interest rates, risk levels, and rotation lengths. Additionally, including natural risks (storms and insects), Dieter (2001) created an economic simulation model for beech and Norway spruce in the site conditions of southern Germany. He used the Faustmann approach and simulated forest growth. Creedy & Wurzbacher (2001) also used the Faustmann approach for modelling the economic value of forested areas of the Thomson Catchment in Central Gippsland, Australia. They computed the timber value at a certain age by multiplying stumpage prices with the output of a timber growth function.

Garcia-Gonzalo et al. (2007) used a process-based ecosystem model (FinnFor) to analyse the effects of climate change and management on timber yield and NPV. The scale of their study was limited to a management unit of ca. 1450 ha in central Finland. The authors ran NPV simulations for Scots pine, Norway spruce and silver birch.

Even if the above mentioned studies did not aim at mapping economic indicators, they are valuable examples of NPV or LEV computation for the economic assessment of tree species or management scenarios. All in all, the studies that computed and mapped the NPV used various methods for estimating costs and benefits. Apparently, the wider the spatial extent of the study, the less complex the method. Presently, there are no studies aimed at mapping NPV for forests across the whole of Finland at 100×100 m spatial resolution, the task that was addressed in this study. In the second chapter further details are provided about the NPV method and its equal annual equivalent (EAE), NPV computation, three approaches of computing benefits for forests in Finland considering their growth, and mapping the NPV for Finnish forests at one hectare forest stand spatial resolution.

1.3. Aim, scope and significance of the study

While there are many studies focused on estimating the value of various ESS, few aspired to map such values at a fine spatial resolution. To date, there are no studies tackling the mapping of the NPV or its EAE for the entire Finnish forests at fine spatial resolution. Finland was an appealing case study because of the available and free data. In this Master's thesis I aimed at investigating the development of NPV and EAE maps of pure cultivated stands in Finland. In order to achieve this aim, I used various datasets coming from the national forest inventory of 2011. The NPV and its EAE were modelled and mapped for various stand types across Finland at 100×100 m spatial resolution.

The study is narrowed down to valuating wood timber provision. There is a need for such limitation because assessing the total value of forests is a complex process, which demands access to various data. Integrating other forest ecosystem services could form the aim of further research.

One intended outcome of the study, on a theoretical level, is to contribute to the growing research trend of ESS and FESS valuation studies. Specifically, I focus on mapping the economic value of Finnish forests at the hectare level. Consequently, this study represents a spatial valuation approach of wood provisioning in Finnish forests. A second intended outcome of the study is to clarify benefit estimation methods. Specifically, I focus on three methods for estimating the total standing volume used in the computation of benefits. Finally, a third concern in the research is the detection of differences in terms of profitability between species and site conditions. Thus, to assess which species and site conditions are economically feasible.

2. Material and methods

The previous chapter broadly introduced the general concept of economic valuation of ecosystem services, with a focus on forest ecosystem services related to timber provisioning. As pointed out earlier, computing the NPV is a common method in forest valuation and its annualized form (EAE) allows a better comparison of investments with different time spans. In this chapter, computing and mapping of two economic indicators for Finnish forests are presented. Their computation required detailed information regarding forest stand growth, stand management and economic data (stumpage prices and management costs).

2.1. Data acquisition and description

Data regarding average stumpage prices and silvicultural management costs by forestry centres³ were retrieved from the Finnish statistical yearbook of forestry (Ylitalo 2011). Details are provided in Appendix 2. The spatial distribution of the 14 forestry centres across Finland (Figure 3) was built using the Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics - NUTS 2010 (EC 2010).

In this study, three methods were used for obtaining forest stand growth data:

- predicting stand growth with yield functions, based on the Multi-source National Forest Inventory Raster Maps (METLA 2013a), hereafter MS-NFI;
- using the EFISCEN inventory database (Sevola 1997; Schelhaas et al. 2006);
- using the MOTTI forest stand simulator (LUKE 2015a), which also provided guidelines for the stand management operations.

Datasets for predicting stand growth with yield functions

The MS-NFI covers the entire country (Figure 1 and Figure 2) and consists of thematic forest maps in georeferenced raster format. The raster maps are set in the ETRS-TM35FIN coordinate system and have a spatial resolution of 20×20 m (Tomppo et al. 2011). They are provided in GeoTIFF format and can be downloaded using a UTM 200 division grid (METLA 2013b). There are a total of 37 tiles defined by

³ Regional forest districts are mentioned as 'forestry centres' in the Finnish statistical yearbook of forestry. The term 'forestry centre' was adopted in this study.

the UTM grid over Finland. The raster datasets contain the total volume (m^3/ha), age (years), canopy cover (percent) and the main site class. The total volume is available for four species groups: Scots pine, Norway spruce, birch and other broad-leaved trees (Figure 2). Metadata is provided in Appendix 1. The four site classes can be interpreted similarly to those used in the EFISCEN inventory database for Finland: site 1 - grass herb forest, site 2 - *Myrtillus* or *Hylocomium-Myrtillus* type, site 3 - *Vaccinium* or *Empetrum-Myrtillus* type and site 4 - *Calluna* or *Cladina* type (Kuusipalo in Yrjölä 2002).

Moreover, two types of soil conditions were considered: mineral soil and peatland. A soil raster layer was retrieved from the European Soil Database (EC 2004) and was further clipped to the extent of Finland (Figure 4A). These thematic soil maps are grids in the ETRS89 Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area (ETRS_LAEA) coordinate system with a spatial resolution of 1×1 km.

The EFISCEN inventory database

The EFISCEN inventory database provides average standing volumes for pure, even-aged stands across several age classes for the same species groups as in MS-NFI. The database differentiates between southern and northern Finland, two types of soil conditions, mineral soil and peatland and four site classes (as described above for MS-NFI). In the present study, these tables were treated as yield tables, even though they only describe the state of the forests at the time of forest inventory.

The MOTTI forest stand simulator⁴

MOTTI is a forest stand simulator which was built to simulate stand development under alternative management regimes and growth conditions in Finland (Hynynen 2002; Salminen, H., Lehtonen, M., & Hynynen 2005). Additionally, MOTTI can compute the profitability of forest management (NPV) and even support biodiversity and carbon sequestration analyses. MOTTI is equipped with distance-independent individual-tree growth models that can predict tree growth (diameter and height) and mortality rates for 5-year periods. It is calibrated to be applicable to all growth conditions across Finland. (Hynynen et al. 2005).

⁴ MOTTI version 3.3.1, downloadable from <http://www.metla.fi/metinfo/motti/motti-asennus-en.htm>.

Figure 1 - Multi-source National Forest Inventory Raster Maps: A) site classes; B) stand age; C) canopy cover.

Figure 2 - Multi-source National Forest Inventory Raster Maps - Total volume (m³/ha) for: A) Scots pine; B) Norway spruce; C) Birch; D) Other broad-leaved species.

2.2. Data processing for the computation and mapping of profitability indices

2.2.1. Geoprocessing the raw spatial data

The geoprocessing work was carried out with ArcMap (ESRI 2013). All outputs were saved into a file geo-database under the ETRS-TM35FIN coordinate system. Whenever possible, the pixel depth of the raster datasets was reduced with the 'Copy Raster' tool (e.g. from 32 to 16 or 8 bit) in order to save computation time and memory usage.

Geoprocessing the MS-NFI datasets

The 'Mosaic To New Raster' tool was used to merge the 37 tiles composing each thematic map covering Finland. In the original datasets, the extreme pixel values of 32766 and 32767 represent missing and null values⁵, respectively. These extreme values together with the zero values were deleted using the 'Set Null' tool with the expression $VALUE = 0 \text{ OR } VALUE = 32766 \text{ OR } VALUE = 32767$. In case of the canopy cover raster dataset, where the maximum meaningful value can only be 100 (meaning 100% canopy cover), the following expression had to be used $VALUE = 0 \text{ OR } VALUE > 100$. The raster datasets were resampled from 20×20 m to the coarser resolution of 100×100 m, so that one cell would represent one hectare of forested area. This operation is thought to reduce the influence of estimation errors and improve accuracy (Talkkari A. 2015, pers. comm.). Katila (2004) offered a detailed assessment regarding the error in the estimates of the Finnish Multisource National Forest Inventory. The resampling operation also has other important advantages: (i) the minimum area of 0.5 ha imposed by international definitions of forest land (FAO 1998) is respected, and (ii) allows the spatial scale considered in this study to agree with the average size of managed stands in southern Finland, which is 1.2 ha (METLA 2012b). These raster datasets were resampled using 'Resample' tool with a bilinear resampling technique. The grid providing site quality information was split according to its four classes using the 'Extract by Attributes' tool. As a result, four raster datasets were obtained, one for each site class. The maps that resulted from geoprocessing the MS-NFI dataset are displayed in Figure 1 and Figure 2 above.

⁵ 32766 (missing value): 'the pixel belongs to forestry land but without satellite image cover'; 32767 (null value): 'the pixel does not belong to forestry land or is outside of the country' (METLA 2013a).

Geoprocessing the NUTS 2010 dataset

The database of Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics - NUTS 2010 (EC 2010) provides boundaries for the administrative units of all EU member countries. The original dataset is a shapefile in the GCS-ETRS-1989 coordinate system, covering the entire European continent at a scale of 1:3 million. In order to select only administrative units belonging to Finland, the 'Select by Attributes' tool, with the selection statement "*NUTS_ID*" LIKE 'FI%' was used (Figure 3A).

Figure 3 - Administrative borders: A) NUTS 2010; B) Forestry centres and regions of Finland.

The differentiation between northern and southern regions (Figure 3B) was based on the information provided by the database of NUTS 2010 and the map of the sampling design areas for MS-NFI (METLA 2011). Furthermore, the map displaying the approximate distribution of the 14 forestry centres across Finland (Figure 3B) was built using the database of NUTS 2010 and spatial information from the Finnish statistical yearbook of forestry (Ylitalo 2011). Certain NUTS 2010 administrative units were aggregated to form desired forestry centres (Appendix 3, Table 12).

The feature datasets were transformed to raster datasets using 'Feature to Raster' tool with a resolution of 100×100 m. Their coordinate system was changed from GCS-ETRS-1989 to ETRS-TM35FIN using 'Project Raster' tool so that they would be in accordance with the MS-NFI dataset. After changing the coordinate system and the resolution there was a minor spatial shift between these raster datasets and the MS-NFI dataset. Therefore, the 'Shift' tool was used in order to reduce the displacement. More details about the shifting procedure are given in Appendix 3.

Geoprocessing the soil raster dataset

The European Soil Database (EC 2004) provides thematic soil maps for Europe in the form of a grid in the ETRS89 Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area (ETRS_LAEA) coordinate system at a spatial resolution of 1×1 km. The original raster dataset was clipped with the 'Extract By Mask' tool to the extent of Finland (Figure 4A). The NUTS 2010 shapefile of Finland (Figure 3A) was used as a mask for clipping. In order to make it compatible with the EFISCEN yield tables, the soil classes cambisol, fluvisol, gleysol, leptosol, podzoluvisol, planosol and podzol were aggregated into the wider soil class of mineral soils. Peatlands are represented by histosols. Consequently, only two soil classes were considered, i.e. mineral soils and peatlands (Figure 4B).

In order to ensure compatibility with the MS-NFI dataset, the coordinate system of the soil grid was changed to ETRS-TM35FIN using the 'Project Raster' tool. Additionally, the resolution was resampled to 100×100 m using the 'Resample' tool with the nearest neighbour resampling technique. There was a minor spatial shift between the new soil raster datasets and the MS-NFI datasets. The 'Shift' tool was used in order to adjust for the displacement (Appendix 4).

Because the original resolution of the soil raster dataset (1×1 km) was coarser than that of the geoprocessed MS-NFI datasets (100×100 m), some mismatches appeared around water bodies when overlapping the two datasets (Figure 26 in Appendix 4). This issue was tackled by filling the mismatching gaps with estimated neighbouring soil values. Further details are given in Appendix 4. The final soil raster dataset was split according to its two soil attributes using the 'Extract by Attributes' tool. Consequently, two grids were obtained, one depicting mineral soils and the other peatlands across Finland.

Figure 4 - Aggregation of all soil types into mineral soils and peatlands. A) Soil conditions as retrieved from the European Soil Database (EC 2004); B) Aggregated soils.

2.2.2. Defining forest stand addresses (FSA)

The following variables were coded at the raster cell (i.e. stand) level: species (four groups), site quality (four classes), soil (two classes), forestry centre (14 levels), region (2 levels). For each cell this information was aggregated in a code (Figure 5). Summing up all variables grids lead to a final raster dataset depicting the forest stand addresses (FSA), which later allowed the mapping of the net present value (NPV). The FSA raster dataset was clipped with the grid of the dominant species (Figure 5A). Eighty addresses were artefacts of geoprocessing and were deleted (cells belonging to the forestry centres 0, 7, 8, 9 and 10 that were recorded in the northern region and cells belonging to the forestry centres 11 and 12 that were recorded in the southern region). The artefacts were eliminated by using the 'Extract by Attributes' tool with the clause *Value* ≥ 111111 AND *Value* ≤ 210244 . For each of the remaining 417 unique FSA (grid attributes) a NPV could be further computed.

Figure 5 - Depicting growth conditions and regions as codes. A) Codes assigned to dominant species. B) Codes assigned to site classes. C) Codes assigned to soil classes. D) Codes assigned to regions and forestry centres.

Defining dominant species stands and their codes

A forest stand was represented by a cell of 100×100 m (1 ha). Because all four species could be present in one stand, the species with the highest relative contribution to total standing volume was defined as the dominant species. For example, if a stand had a total volume of 100 m³/ha and the stand composition was 50 m³/ha pine, 40 m³/ha spruce and 10 m³/ha birch, then pine was considered the dominant species. Subsequently, the NPV would be computed for the cash flow of managing a pine stand. Such simplification had to be made given the complex dynamics of mixed stands and the limited scope of this study. For the purpose of finding the dominant species in each stand, a Python script was built and run in the Python window of ArcMap (script given in Appendix 5). Essentially, the script detects the maximum volume at the stand level (one cell), then tests to which species this maximum value belongs to, and returns a presence-absence grid for each species (Figure 6 B, C, D, E). Finally, all these raster datasets are merged together and a code is attributed to each species (Figure 6A).

Figure 6 - Dominant species stands. A) All dominant species stands with corresponding codes; B) Scots pine stands; C) Birch stands; D) Norway spruce stands; E) Other broad-leaved trees stands.

Defining codes for the four site classes

The site classes within the geoprocessed MS-NFI datasets are coded as 1, 2, 3 and 4. In order to distinguish them from the species codes defined above, the cell values of the site classes raster dataset (Figure 1A) were changed to 10, 20, 30 and 40 with the 'Reclassify' tool (Figure 5B).

Defining codes for the two soil classes

Using the 'Reclassify' tool, the cell values of the soil classes raster dataset (Figure 4B) were changed as follows: 100 for mineral soils and 200 for peatlands (Figure 5C).

Defining codes for the forestry centres and regions

There are 14 forestry centres across Finland and their default codes (Figure 3B) are given in the Finnish statistical yearbook of forestry (Ylitalo 2011). The 'Reclassify' tool was used to assign new codes (Figure 5D). In the same manner, 100 000 was assigned to northern Finland and 200 000 to southern Finland (Figure 5D).

2.2.3. Predicting stand growth with yield functions

General considerations

Regional yield functions were computed using the MS-NFI datasets. There were 16 site conditions which resulted from considering all combinations of the two regions (northern and southern Finland) and the two soil classes (mineral soils and peatlands) for each of the four site classes. As each of the 16 site types had to be considered for each of the four species groups, a total of 64 regional yield functions were computed.

Spatial processing of growth conditions

Considering a resolution of 100×100 m (1 ha), a raster cell represented a forest stand. Initially, the goal was to compute yield functions only for pure stands. However, this was not possible due to the small number of observations available for some combinations of species and site types. Consequently, stands with some mixing and mixed stands had to also be considered and their definition is given in Table 1.

Generally, stands with a canopy cover higher than the third quartile of the canopy cover distribution were considered for yield function computation. If there were still not

enough stands in order to observe a pattern for a yield curve to be computed, then the median or the first quartile were considered (e.g. on site classes 4 or 3 where canopy cover was usually low). The analysis concerning canopy cover was carried out in R (R Development Core Team 2015).

Table 1 - Type of stands considered for defining regional yield functions

Type of stands	Dominant species' share of stand total volume
Pure stands	over 95%.
Pure stands and stands with some mixing	over 75%
Pure stands, stands with some mixing and mixed stands	over 50%

NOTE: Adapted from (METLA 2012a)

The diagram in Figure 7 illustrates the entire process of building regional yield functions for the four species across Finland. The process involved using various pre-defined ArcGIS tools, user-defined Model Builder tools, R (R Development Core Team 2015) and Python (Python Software Foundation 2015) code. Scripts are provided in Appendix 6 and 7. Shortly, the procedure consisted in segregating stands by regions, soil classes, site classes, tree species and imposing certain thresholds for volume and canopy. Appendix 8 illustrates the yield curves computed for each site and provides details about the volume and canopy cover thresholds.

Two models (tools) were built with the Model Builder application of ArcMap. One model extracts the canopy cover of the forest stands on each regionalized site for each species. The workflow of this model is presented by the diagram in Figure 8. The second model tabulates volume by age for every forest stand on every regionalized site. The workflow is presented by the diagram in Figure 9.

Figure 7- Workflow for computing regional yield functions.

Figure 8 - Workflow of the model which extracts the canopy cover of forest.

Nonlinear regression modelling and model selection for yield functions

A common way to model volume growth in even-aged stands is to use various nonlinear functions of the form $v=f(a)$, where v is the stand volume (m^3/ha) and a is the stand age (years). In this study the logistic and Gompertz functions were used. Both are sigmoid functions which reflect well-known stand dynamics, i.e. that growth rates increase during early developmental stages, reach a maximum, and then decrease in mature and over-mature stands. The equation of the logistic function used in this study is given by Eq. 1, where v is the stand volume, age is the stand age, $Asym$, $xmid$ and $scal$ are parameters.

$$v = \frac{Asym}{1 + e^{(xmid-age)/scal}} \quad (Eq. 1)$$

The logistic function is symmetric about the inflection point ($age=xmid$, $v=Asym/2$) and presents an asymptote at $v=Asym$ (Vera Sit, Melanie Poulin-Costello 1994). The equation of the Gompertz function is described by Eq. 2, where v is the stand volume, age is the stand age, $Asym$, $b2$ and $b3$ are parameters.

$$v = Asym \cdot e^{-b2 \cdot b3^{age}} \quad (Eq. 2)$$

Gompertz function is not symmetric about an inflection point and has asymptotes at $v=0$ and $v=Asym$ (Vera Sit, Melanie Poulin-Costello 1994).

Figure 9 - Workflow of the model which tabulates volume by age for forest stands.

For both cases the functional form can be linearized by a log-transformation if the parameter *Asym* is known. In this study, no transformation was applied and the estimates for the parameters of the models were obtained by using the nonlinear least squares technique.

The nonlinear regression analysis was conducted in R, using the functions *nls* and *nls2* from the libraries *stats* and *nls2*, respectively. The code is provided in Appendix 7 and statistical results regarding the coefficient estimates are provided in Appendix 9. Whenever possible, the self-starting R functions *SSlogis* and *SSgompertz* were used. When they failed to converge and find estimates for the parameters, naive guesses were made for the starting values and/or the convergence algorithm was adjusted

(e.g. gradually increasing the number of iterations or the convergence tolerance). Only models with significant estimates (five percent significance level) were kept for further investigation and statistical inference. Gompertz and logistic models were compared using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). The preferred model was the one with a smaller AIC value. A model selection approach similar to the one proposed by Burnham & Anderson (2002) was used. The authors suggest the rule of thumb according to which models with AIC difference smaller or equal than 2 ($\Delta AIC \leq 2$) have substantial empirical support, those with $4 \leq \Delta AIC \leq 7$ have considerably less and those with $\Delta AIC > 10$ have essentially none. On the other hand, they also suggest that the model with $\Delta AIC > 10$ might still be used for inference if the sample size is large. Additionally, the under-fitting or over-fitting of the data by the analysed models were very important criteria for model selection. This was assessed visually using the figures of Appendix 8.

2.2.4. Forest stand management and simulation with MOTTI

Running the MOTTI simulator involved the following steps: stand initialization, running the automatic stand simulation and saving the results as Excel files. The workflow for the MOTTI simulations is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10 - Workflow for MOTTI simulations.

Stand initialization required choosing a location out of 351 possible municipalities across Finland. Each municipality was characterized based on the following growth factors: temperature sum, latitude, longitude and altitude. Theoretically, all 32 stand conditions⁶ could have been considered for each of the 351 municipalities. However, running MOTTI so many times would have been extremely cumbersome. Consequently, the analysis was narrowed down to two representative municipalities: Orivesi and Pudasjärvi for southern and northern conditions, respectively. This resulted in 64 MOTTI simulations comparable with the 64 defined regional yield functions and the EFISCEN tables. The two locations were in the interval described by 0.1 standard deviations from the average conditions⁷ of south and north Finland. An R script was used in order to automate the selection. The next step in stand initialization was to choose the site type. A correspondence was established between the site conditions considered in the EFISCEN database and the MS-NFI, on the one hand, and the site types used by the MOTTI simulator, on the other hand (Figure 10). Descriptions of the site factors used in MOTTI were provided by The Natural Resources Institute Finland (Salminen H. 2015, pers. comm.). All stands were artificially established (option 'Established stand') and the plantation density was adjusted to 2000 seedlings per hectare for spruce, pine and other broad-leaved species, and 1600 seedlings/ha for silver birch (Niskanen 1999). All other options related to stand initialization were kept unchanged.

Concerning stand simulation, the MOTTI simulator considers by default the practical management recommendations for private forests issued by the Forestry Development Centre Tapio (LUKE 2015b). The management of a forest stand can include the following silvicultural operations: artificial regeneration, cleaning (for stands in the sapling stage), pre-commercial thinning, commercial thinning and a clear cut at the end of the management cycle. The artificial regeneration and the final cut are obligatory operations, while the others are optional.

⁶ The 32 growth conditions are given by the four group tree species (Scots pine, Norway spruce, birch, other broad-leaved trees), four site classes and two soil classes (mineral soils and peatlands).

⁷ Temperature sum and latitude were used for the north region. The longitude was additionally used for the south region in order to narrow down the location options only to one.

Running MOTTI for the 64 site conditions resulted in 64 *.xls-files. These files were processed with R and the resulting management guidelines for the 64 stand types are provided in Appendix 10. These guidelines offer details about the timing (stand age) of the silvicultural operations and about the harvestable wood volumes (%) per operation for each of the two considered assortments, i.e. logs and pulpwood.

2.3. Computation and mapping of profitability indices

2.3.1. The concept of net present value (NPV) and its equal annual equivalent (EAE) in forest stand management

Computing present values requires the use of discount rates (d) and both future benefits (B) and costs (C) have to be discounted to the present moment. The future benefits (€/ha) are actually the product between stumpage prices (€/m³) and standing timber (m³/ha) at a certain moment (t). Consequently, yield functions or tables detailing the development of a forest stands are required (Figure 11).

Figure 11 - A model of stand management cycle. Modified from Saramäki (2012).

The net present value (NPV) is mathematically defined as:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{B_t}{(1+d)^t} - \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{C_t}{(1+d)^t}, [\text{€/ha}]$$

where T is stand age (years) at the moment of the final cut (clear cut), d is the discount rate, and B_t and C_t represent the benefits and the costs (€/ha) in the year t . A positive NPV indicates a profitable investment.

The annualised form of the NPV, the equal annual equivalent (EAE) has the advantage that it makes investments with different time spans comparable. Consequently, differences in the rotation lengths imposed by species, site conditions or other criteria can be neglected when using EAE. Additionally, it allows comparisons between annual returns per hectare from forest land with those from other types of land use (e.g. agriculture). The equal annual equivalent (EAE) is mathematically defined as:

$$EAE = NPV \cdot \left(\frac{d \cdot (1 + d)^T}{(1 + d)^T - 1} \right), [\text{€} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{year}^{-1}]$$

where T is stand age (years) at the moment of the final cut (clear cut), d is the discount rate and NPV is the net present value. As in the case of NPV, a positive EAE indicates a profitable forest stand.

2.3.2. NPV and EAE computation

The NPV computation applied in this study is valid for even-aged stands, dominated by one species. Additionally, the stands need to be treated with a clear cut at the end of the management cycle and always artificially regenerated.

As mentioned in the section 2.2.2., the variables: dominant species, site class, soil class, forestry centre and region, were coded at the raster cell level. For each of the designated forest stand addresses (417 in total) the NPV could be computed based on available information related to wood prices, management costs, discount rate, stand management operations and forest yield. An R script was written to retrieve the above mentioned information from several *.txt files and calculate the NPVs and then the corresponding EAEs. The diagram in Figure 12 illustrates the applied workflow.

Cleaning and *pre-commercial thinning* are operations applied in young stands which aim to improve the future quality of the mature trees. They bring no immediate benefits, but they do generate costs.

Figure 12 - Workflow describing NPV computation. The standing volume for calculating the benefits was obtained by using tree methods: running the MOTTI simulator, computing regional yield functions and from the EFISCEN inventory database.

Costs of *artificial regeneration* were computed separately for mineral soils and peatlands. For mineral soils the following silvicultural operations were considered: clearing of regeneration areas, disc trenching and planting. For peatlands the difference consisted in the fact that mounding replaced disc trenching. Indeed, disc trenching is a widely applied soil preparation operation in Finnish forests (Tervo 2000), but peatlands require special measures. The costs were not differentiated by the type of forest property, private or state, instead their average was considered. The average stumpage prices were given only for non-industrial, private forests and differentiated between forestry centres, species and assortments (logs and pulpwood). In Finland, almost 60% of the forest land is private (Saramäki 2012).

An example of computing the NPV for a pine stand on site class 4 with mineral soil from southern Finland, forestry centre 3 is given in Table 2 and Figure 13. In Table 2 the NPV was calculated for two constant discount rates (1% and 3%). It can be noticed that for a 1% discount rate the investment is profitable (NPV = 2815 €/ha) while for a 3% discount rate the investment will not yield profit for the forest owner (NPV= -293 €/ha). Another way of interpreting the NPV is to say that if a buyer paid the NPV amount (e.g. 2815 €/ha) for the forest stand, he or she would earn the discount rate on the investment (e.g. 1%) with the strong assumption that the management plan was respected (Straka 2007).

Table 2 – Example of NPV computation

Operation	Age	Standing volume (m ³ /ha) ¹⁾	Harvested volume (m ³ /ha)		Price (€/m ³)		Cost or benefit (€/ha)	Discounted cost or benefit (€/ha)	
			L ²⁾	P ³⁾	L	P		discount rate	
								1%	3%
Regeneration	0	-	-	-	-	-	-1133	-1133	-1133
Cleaning	-	-	-	-	-	-	0	0	0
Pre-commercial thinning	10	-	-	-	-	-	-452	-409	-336
1st thinning	36	106	-	34	54.7	14.6	496	347	171
2nd thinning	44	111	-	37	54.7	14.6	540	349	147
3rd thinning	63	157	14	38	54.7	14.6	1321	706	205
Final cut	77	153	104	46	54.7	14.6	6360	2956	653
TOTAL (NPV)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2815	-293

1) Standing volumes were provided by the MOTTI simulator

2) Volume of logs assortment

3) Volume of pulpwood assortment

Figure 13 - Example of NPV computation. The management cycle was simulated with MOTTI. The stand is dominated by pine located in southern Finland, forestry centre 3 - Häme-Uusimaa, on site class 4 with mineral soil. The costs and benefits are in their discounted form after applying a discount rate of 1%. The benefits were computed based on the standing volumes that were estimated in three ways: 1) with the MOTTI simulator, 2) using the computed regional yield functions and 3) retrieved from the EFISCEN inventory database.

2.3.3. NPV and EAE mapping

Once the NPVs and the EAEs were computed for the 417 forest stand addresses, they were saved as a tab delimited *.txt file and joined with the corresponding cell addresses in one raster dataset. This implied an inner join operation within ArcMap environment (Figure 14).

Figure 14 - Joining the NPV results with the FSA raster dataset.

2.4. Sensitivity analysis

The purpose was to investigate the effects of the discount rate on species profitability for the three yield estimation methods and the 16 combinations of ecological factors (region: south or north; soil: mineral or peat; site class: 1 to 4). Holopainen & Talvitie (2006) mentioned that 3% and 5% discount rates are usually used for profitability calculations in forest planning. In their sensitivity analysis for the Norwegian forests, Hoen et al. (2001) used three discount rates: 1.5%, 2.5% and 3.5%. In this study, the sensitivity of the EAE was examined along a gradient of nine discount rates, i.e. from 1% to 5%, with a step of 0.5.

2.5. Summary

In this chapter the steps for computing and mapping two profitability indicators for Finnish forests (NPV and EAE) were described. Information regarding forest stand growth was necessary and three methods were used to obtain it: regional yield functions, EFISCEN inventory database and the MOTTI forest stand simulator. The EFISCEN inventory database provided information regarding the standing volumes for several age classes and four species groups across 16 site types. The four species groups were: pine, spruce, birch and other broad-leaved. The site types were given by two regions (south and north), two soil conditions (mineral and peatland) and four site classes for each soil. The same site conditions were considered for building the yield functions and for the MOTTI simulations. Building regional yield functions required intensive data preparation and was based on the Multi-source National Forest Inventory Raster Maps of 2011 (METLA 2013a). Two sigmoid models, logistic and Gompertz, were fitted to the original (i.e. untransformed) data and the 'best' fitting model was selected for further inference. Regarding forest stand management interventions for the simulations with MOTTI, default prescriptions were used.

The economic benefits were computed as the product between the harvested wood quantities and the average stumpage prices. The cash flows (costs and benefits along a management cycle) were discounted with several discount rates leading to NPV and EAE computation. Finally, the two profitability indicators (NPV and EAE) were mapped at 100×100 m spatial resolution across Finland.

3. Results

3.1. Yield estimates for computation of profitability indices

3.1.1. Regional yield functions

Figure 15 shows regional yield curves for the four species groups on 16 site conditions. Reliable regional yield functions could not be computed for ‘other broad-leaved species’ group on all sites. On average, the models indicate that spruce forest stands are characterized by higher standing volumes than other species, especially for southern regions. Generally, independent of species, stands on site class 1 present the highest standing volumes. At the opposite pole are forest stands on site class 4.

Figure 15 - Regional yield curves.

The significant parameter estimates (p -value less than 5% significance level) of the functions together with their statistics are provided in Appendix 9. The graphs from Appendix 8 illustrate the models with the cloud of observations for every site condition.

3.1.2. EFISCEN inventory database

Figure 16 shows standing volumes at various ages as given by the EFISCEN inventory database for Finland. The points connected by lines are located at the centre of age classes. One age class has an amplitude of 20 years. In general, there is an agreement between the information given by the regional yield curves and the EFISCEN data.

Figure 16 - Standing volumes provided by the EFISCEN inventory database. Regional yield curves are plotted in the background.

3.1.3. Forest stand management and simulations with MOTTI

Figure 17 shows the development of forest stands for the four species groups on 16 site conditions considering the default MOTTI forest management guidelines. In general, on mineral soils, standing volumes are visibly higher than those given by regional yield functions. Some exceptions appear on peatlands. The corresponding management guidelines are summarized in a tabular form in Appendix 10. They offer details about the timing of silvicultural operations and about harvestable percentages per operation for each wood assortment, i.e. logs and pulpwood.

Figure 17 - Stand growth and management given by the MOTTI stand simulator. Regional yield curves are plotted in the background.

3.2. Profitability indices

3.2.1. NPVs and EAEs by levels of ecological factors

The 417 unique forest stand addresses (FSAs) defined in section 2.2.2 were considered for analysing. A forest stand dominated by one of the four species groups, depending on its location, could fall within one of the 16 site conditions mentioned in section 2.2.3 and also within one of the 14 forestry centres (896 combinations). Site conditions influenced the standing volume and management, consequently the economic benefits, and the forestry centres dictated the costs and the stumpage prices.

Southern forests are divided into 11 forestry centres, while northern forests are divided into three. Whereas all possible site conditions could exist in every northern forestry centre, in the case of southern centres some sites were not identified (e.g. stands dominated by other broad-leaved on site class 4 with peat appeared only in two southern forestry centres). Due to unbalanced distribution of forestry centres across north and south and unbalanced spatial distribution of site conditions, the 417 FSAs were unevenly distributed when grouped by ecological factors (Table 3). Table 3 also informs about the surfaces corresponding to each of the four species groups within 16 site conditions across Finnish forests.

Average values and standard deviations of the 417 NPVs and EAEs grouped by site conditions and by the three yield estimation methods are presented in Table 4 - Table 9. The values were computed at a discount rate of one percent. Profitability indices (NPV and EAE) could be computed for all type of stands in the case of volume estimations based on MOTTI stand simulator (Table 4 and Table 5). However, some exceptions occurred in the case of estimations based on regional yield functions and EFISCEN inventory database. For example, reliable yield functions could not be computed for other broad-leaved species on all site conditions. (Table 6 and Table 7). Additionally, in the case of EFISCEN inventory database (Table 8 and Table 9), missing data did not allow the computation of profitability indices on all site conditions for other broad-leaved species, spruce and birch.

Table 3 - Number of unique forest stand addresses (FSA) and forest stands (FS) aggregated by levels of ecological factors

Region	Species	Soil: Mineral							
		Site classes							
		S1		S2		S3		S4	
		FSA	FS (ha)	FSA	FS (ha)	FSA	FS (ha)	FSA	FS (ha)
South	Pine	11	4,198,955	11	142,413	11	1,143,336	11	5,056
	Spruce	11	2,769,850	11	184,215	11	27,967	11	1,360
	Birch	11	1,306,327	11	154,690	11	62,398	11	1,815
	Other	11	269,666	11	3,975	10	1,018	8	258
North	Pine	3	3,301,412	3	63,763	3	1,235,616	3	34,561
	Spruce	3	531,257	3	67,283	3	45,869	3	2,061
	Birch	3	822,549	3	136,333	3	124,716	3	3,072
	Other	3	29,906	3	2,234	3	1,825	3	180
Soil: Peat									
South	Pine	10	601,785	10	33,758	10	383,063	10	2,043
	Spruce	10	205,011	10	27,840	10	5,285	9	149
	Birch	10	118,593	10	26,528	10	16,719	9	271
	Other	10	17,199	10	612	9	319	2	5
North	Pine	3	2,578,195	3	69,465	3	1,653,156	3	63,328
	Spruce	3	383,420	3	71,389	3	71,972	3	5,278
	Birch	3	294,250	3	121,976	3	129,542	3	3,769
	Other	3	17,501	3	622	3	2,595	3	178

NOTE: One NPV corresponds to one unique forest stand address (FSA) defined in section 2.2.2. One forest stand (FS) represents one hectare (100×100 m) thus the figures also represent surfaces.

The type of soil (mineral or peat) had a major influence on the mean values of both NPV and EAE profitability indices, independent of species or the method used for yield estimation. Stands on mineral soils were, on average, more profitable than stands on peatlands with most of species not yielding profit on sites with peat. For example, when predicting yield with the MOTTI stand simulator, Scots pine stands on southern S1 sites with mineral soil yielded an EAE up to 243 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ (SD: 28.4 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹). However, the EAE dropped to an unprofitable level of -28 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ (SD: 1.8 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹) on peatlands (Table 5). This shift in profitability due to soil conditions happened for all site classes and for both southern and northern regions. This trend was also observed for the other two yield estimation methods (for regional yield functions - Table 6, Table 7 and for EFISCEN inventory database - Table 8, Table 9).

Only Norway spruce stands remained profitable on peatlands, yielding an average yearly return per hectare up to 181 € (SD: 2.6 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹) on southern peatlands

and 95 € (SD: 4.5 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹) on northern ones (site class S1 - Table 5). However, this profitability abruptly declined from site class S1 to S2, after trickling down without significant variations to S3 and S4. The abrupt decline was independent of region (southern or northern) and yield estimation method. Generally, all species manifested a decline pattern in profitability from site class S1 towards S4.

Another trend in profitability was observed when comparing northern and southern regions. On average, southern stands were more profitable than northern ones. For instance, considering the MOTTI estimations and a discount rate of one percent (Table 5), Scots pine stands on southern site class 1 with mineral soil yielded an EAE of 243 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ but only 104 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ on northern sites. Given the same conditions, the profitability of spruce stands dropped from an EAE of 293 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ on southern sites to 110 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ on northern ones. For both pine and spruce that was a decrease in profitability of around 60%. The EAE of birch stands decreased with 70%, dropping from 109 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ (south) to 32 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ (north). Stands dominated by other broad-leaved went from an EAE of 69 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ (south) to 12 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ (north), which meant a decrease of around 80%. The same decreasing trend was also observed on peatlands, where, for instance, the EAE of spruce stands dropped from 181 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ (south) to 95 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹ (north), meaning a decrease of around 50% (Table 5).

Furthermore, the results show that the standard deviation (S.D.) of both NPV and EAE decreased with decreasing site quality. In general, the S.D. followed the same trend as the one described above.

Table 4 - Summary statistics for NPVs - MOTTI by levels of ecological factors (1% discount rate; yield estimations based on MOTTI simulations)

		Soil: Mineral							
Region	Species	Site classes							
		S1		S2		S3		S4	
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
South	Pine	8,920	1,042	7,435	890	7,313	871	2,861	395
	Spruce	12,016	1,501	12,355	1,543	7,978	1,029	782	186
	Birch	5,168	653	3,480	489	2,608	408	-146	123
	Other	3,271	476	1,699	328	539	85	-330	83
North	Pine	4,737	253	3,628	210	3,727	211	1,315	92
	Spruce	5,847	325	5,279	304	3,274	198	-70	53
	Birch	1,342	458	262	128	111	65	-718	64
	Other	518	97	1	83	-235	76	-735	63
		Soil: Peat							
South	Pine	-1,539	100	-1,469	100	-1,443	100	-1,037	88
	Spruce	9,950	145	2,635	82	1,549	82	2,378	97
	Birch	-720	73	-895	72	-875	72	-904	74
	Other	-420	76	-641	74	-750	77	-676	23
North	Pine	-610	76	-992	43	-1,060	46	-1,055	44
	Spruce	5,088	240	803	72	484	66	618	65
	Birch	-760	85	-892	82	-959	80	-956	80
	Other	-546	90	-854	83	-926	81	-909	81

NOTE: Mean and standard deviation (S.D.) expressed in €/ha

Table 5 - Summary statistics for EAEs - MOTTI by levels of ecological factors (1% discount rate; yield estimations based on MOTTI simulations)

		Soil: Mineral							
Region	Species	Site classes							
		S1		S2		S3		S4	
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
South	Pine	242.9	28.4	152.8	18.3	147.2	17.5	53.5	7.4
	Spruce	293.2	36.6	262.3	32.8	173.3	22.3	14.2	3.4
	Birch	108.5	13.7	73.1	10.3	54.8	8.6	-3.1	2.6
	Other	68.7	10.0	35.7	6.9	11.3	1.8	-6.9	1.8
North	Pine	104.1	5.6	62.2	3.6	59.8	3.4	18.8	1.3
	Spruce	110.2	6.1	91.1	5.2	54.6	3.3	-1.0	0.8
	Birch	31.8	10.9	6.2	3.0	2.6	1.5	-17.0	1.5
	Other	12.3	2.3	0.0	2.0	-5.6	1.8	-17.4	1.5
		Soil: Peat							
South	Pine	-28.0	1.8	-26.8	1.8	-24.4	1.7	-16.0	1.4
	Spruce	181.3	2.6	48.0	1.5	28.2	1.5	43.3	1.8
	Birch	-15.1	1.5	-18.8	1.5	-18.4	1.5	-19.0	1.6
	Other	-8.8	1.6	-13.5	1.5	-15.7	1.6	-14.2	0.5
North	Pine	-9.4	1.2	-15.3	0.7	-15.6	0.7	-14.3	0.6
	Spruce	95.1	4.5	11.5	1.0	6.9	0.9	8.9	0.9
	Birch	-18.0	2.0	-21.2	1.9	-22.8	1.9	-22.7	1.9
	Other	-13.0	2.1	-20.3	2.0	-22.0	1.9	-21.6	1.9

NOTE: Mean and standard deviation (S.D.) expressed in € ha⁻¹year⁻¹.

Table 6 - Summary statistics for NPVs - Yield Functions by levels of ecological factors (1% discount rate; yield estimations based on regional yield functions)

		Soil: Mineral							
Region	Species	Site classes							
		S1		S2		S3		S4	
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
South	Pine	1,733	291	818	201	2,368	357	1,249	234
	Spruce	6,034	812	5,336	732	1,243	260	84	117
	Birch	1,038	222	605	183	187	145	-802	66
	Other	1,944	332	465	181	-	-	-	-
North	Pine	1,719	125	1,046	100	987	92	-700	25
	Spruce	1,775	146	1,211	122	-1,022	26	-563	57
	Birch	-84	206	-355	82	-524	47	-714	64
	Other	-20	82	-399	72	-	-	-	-
		Soil: Peat							
South	Pine	-1,086	105	-1,276	102	-1,229	102	-1,142	86
	Spruce	6,230	108	2,048	80	222	69	553	70
	Birch	-356	76	-403	76	-765	73	-1,068	73
	Other	257	85	-513	75	-	-	-	-
North	Pine	-422	74	-937	42	-981	45	-1,280	46
	Spruce	1,693	111	179	48	-570	75	-467	74
	Birch	-590	89	-760	85	-932	81	-964	80
	Other	-761	85	-	-	-	-	-	-

NOTE: Mean and standard deviation (S.D.) expressed in €/ha

Table 7 - Summary statistics for EAEs - Yield Functions by levels of ecological factors (1% discount rate; yield estimations based on regional yield functions)

		Soil: Mineral							
Region	Species	Site classes							
		S1		S2		S3		S4	
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
South	Pine	47.2	7.9	16.8	4.1	47.7	7.2	23.3	4.4
	Spruce	147.2	19.8	113.3	15.5	27.0	5.7	1.5	2.1
	Birch	21.8	4.7	12.7	3.8	3.9	3.1	-16.8	1.4
	Other	40.8	7.0	9.8	3.8	-	-	-	-
North	Pine	37.8	2.7	17.9	1.7	15.8	1.5	-10.0	0.4
	Spruce	33.5	2.7	20.9	2.1	-17.0	0.4	-8.1	0.8
	Birch	-2.0	4.9	-8.4	1.9	-12.4	1.1	-16.9	1.5
	Other	-0.5	2.0	-9.5	1.7	-	-	-	-
		Soil: Peat							
South	Pine	-19.8	1.9	-23.2	1.9	-20.8	1.7	-17.6	1.3
	Spruce	113.5	2.0	37.3	1.4	4.0	1.3	10.1	1.3
	Birch	-7.5	1.6	-8.5	1.6	-16.1	1.5	-22.4	1.5
	Other	5.4	1.8	-10.8	1.6	-	-	-	-
North	Pine	-6.5	1.1	-14.4	0.7	-14.4	0.7	-17.3	0.6
	Spruce	31.6	2.1	2.6	0.7	-8.2	1.1	-6.7	1.1
	Birch	-14.0	2.1	-18.0	2.0	-22.1	1.9	-22.9	1.9
	Other	-18.1	2.0	-	-	-	-	-	-

NOTE: Mean and standard deviation (S.D.) expressed in € ha⁻¹year⁻¹.

Table 8 - Summary statistics for NPVs - EFISCEN by levels of ecological factors (1% discount rate; yield estimations based on EFISCEN inventory database)

		Soil: Mineral							
Region	Species	Site classes							
		S1		S2		S3		S4	
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
South	Pine	4,223	549	3,371	461	2,427	363	557	167
	Spruce	6,016	811	4,143	597	1,333	274	29	112
	Birch	1,776	292	1,321	254	380	161	-830	65
	Other	2,512	388	1,084	253	-	-	-	-
North	Pine	3,334	201	1,538	122	450	70	-14	47
	Spruce	2,052	162	866	114	-836	30	-	-
	Birch	60	221	-768	51	-1,054	32	-817	61
	Other	258	90	-359	73	-	-	-	-
		Soil: Peat							
South	Pine	-977	106	-1,100	104	-1,359	101	-1,215	85
	Spruce	4,334	93	1,026	79	20	68	-	-
	Birch	-81	80	-245	78	-763	73	-926	74
	Other	-215	78	-	-	-	-	-	-
North	Pine	-517	75	-843	41	-1,032	46	-1,185	45
	Spruce	740	67	-36	43	-352	73	-	-
	Birch	-648	88	-819	84	-956	80	-	-
	Other	-333	95	-	-	-	-	-	-

NOTE: Mean and standard deviation (S.D.) expressed in €/ha

Table 9 - Summary statistics for EAEs - EFISCEN by levels of ecological factors (1% discount rate; yield estimations based on EFISCEN inventory database)

		Soil: Mineral							
Region	Species	Site classes							
		S1		S2		S3		S4	
		Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
South	Pine	115.0	14.9	69.3	9.5	48.9	7.3	10.4	3.1
	Spruce	146.8	19.8	88.0	12.7	28.9	5.9	0.5	2.0
	Birch	37.3	6.1	27.7	5.3	8.0	3.4	-17.4	1.4
	Other	52.8	8.1	22.8	5.3	-	-	-	-
North	Pine	73.3	4.4	26.4	2.1	7.2	1.1	-0.2	0.7
	Spruce	38.7	3.1	15.0	2.0	-13.9	0.5	-	-
	Birch	1.4	5.2	-18.2	1.2	-25.0	0.8	-19.4	1.4
	Other	6.1	2.1	-8.5	1.7	-	-	-	-
		Soil: Peat							
South	Pine	-17.8	1.9	-20.0	1.9	-23.0	1.7	-18.7	1.3
	Spruce	79.0	1.7	18.7	1.4	0.4	1.2	-	-
	Birch	-1.7	1.7	-5.1	1.6	-16.0	1.5	-19.4	1.6
	Other	-4.5	1.6	-	-	-	-	-	-
North	Pine	-8.0	1.2	-13.0	0.6	-15.1	0.7	-16.0	0.6
	Spruce	13.8	1.3	-0.5	0.6	-5.1	1.0	-	-
	Birch	-15.4	2.1	-19.4	2.0	-22.7	1.9	-	-
	Other	-7.9	2.3	-	-	-	-	-	-

NOTE: Mean and standard deviation (S.D.) expressed in € ha⁻¹year⁻¹.

3.2.2. Sensitivity of the equal annual equivalent (EAE)

The discount rate considerably influenced the EAE profitability index. As expected, the average yearly return per hectare indicated by EAE decreased with increasing discount rate, independent of species, ecological factor or yield estimation method (Figure 18- Figure 22).

For Scots pine (Figure 18) the decline in profitability was exponential on sites with mineral soil and linear on peatlands. Stands on peatlands were not profitable at any discount rate. However, for MOTTI simulations, the southern stands on site class 1 with mineral soil were profitable even at a discount rate of five percent.

Figure 18 - The EAE sensitivity of Scots pine to yield estimation method and discount rate by ecological factors.

Differences in profitability level due to yield estimation methods were more distinct on mineral soils than on peatlands. The EAE on mineral soils was distinctively higher when considering the MOTTI yield estimations. On mineral soils, the EAE fell off when using the EFISCEN inventory database and decreased further for the estimations given by the regional yield functions. On mineral soils, differences in profitability due to yield estimation methods were more distinct on southern sites than on northern ones. Additionally, these differences became less distinct from site class 1 towards site class 4. This trend was more evident for southern forest stands, which on average, were more profitable.

In the case of Norway spruce (Figure 19) the decrease in profitability was exponential both on mineral soil and peatlands. For the MOTTI simulations, all types of spruce stands were profitable at a discount rate of one percent, including stands on peatlands. Additionally, the southern stands on site class 1 with mineral soil were profitable even at a discount rate of five percent. These type of southern stands cover 2.8 million ha out of the 4.4 million ha of all spruce stands across Finland (Table 3). As in the case of pine, differences in profitability due to yield estimation methods were, on average, more distinct on mineral soils than on peatlands. However, for spruce the differences remained distinct for all stands on site class 1, independent of soil conditions. In contrast, for stands on site class 4 the differences in profitability were significantly less distinct. Note, however, that missing data in the EFISCEN inventory database did not allow the computation of profitability indices for some stands on site class 4.

On the whole, the EAE was noticeably higher for MOTTI simulations. The EAE fell off roughly at the same level when using yield estimations given by both the EFISCEN inventory database and the regional yield functions. Thus, differences between the EAEs due to these two yield estimation methods were, on average, less distinguishable. As in the case of pine, on mineral soils, differences in profitability due to yield estimation methods were more distinct on southern sites than on northern ones. These differences became less distinct from site class 1 towards site class 4.

Figure 19 - The EAE sensitivity of Norway spruce to yield estimation method and discount rate by ecological factors.

In the case of birch (Figure 20), the decline in profitability was rather linear on all site conditions. Stands on peatlands were not profitable at any discount rate. Similarly, stands on site class 4 were not yielding profit independent of other factors. As in the case of pine and spruce, profitability differences due to yield estimation methods were, on average, more distinct on mineral soils than on peatlands. For stands on site class 4, both with mineral soils and peatlands, the profitability differences were significantly less distinct than on the other site classes. Missing data in the EFISCEN inventory database did not allow the computation of profitability indices for northern stands on site class 4 with peat.

All in all, the EAE was noticeably higher for MOTTI simulations. Furthermore, there were no clearly distinguishable differences between the EAEs given by the EFISCEN inventory database and the regional yield functions. As in the case of pine and spruce, on mineral soils, profitability differences due to yield estimation methods were more distinct on southern sites than on northern ones. These differences became less distinct from site class 1 towards site class 4.

Figure 20 - The EAE sensitivity of birch to yield estimation method and discount rate by ecological factors.

Figure 21 - The EAE sensitivity of other broad-leaved species to yield estimation method and discount rate by ecological factors.

In the case of other broad-leaved species (Figure 21), the decline in profitability was linear on all site conditions. In general, stands on peatlands were not profitable. However, an exception occurred for the southern stands on site class 1 at one percent discount rate, where EAE was $5.4 \text{ € ha}^{-1}\text{year}^{-1}$ (SD: $1.8 \text{ € ha}^{-1}\text{year}^{-1}$) for the regional yield functions estimates (also see Table 7). Stands on site class 4 were not yielding profit at any discount rate independent of other factors. Contrasting the case of previous species, differences in profitability level due to the yield estimation methods were rather undistinguishable on all site conditions. However, some differences could be detected for southern stands on site classes 1 and 2 with mineral soil, where MOTTI simulations indicated higher profitability than other yield estimation methods.

As mentioned in the previous section, missing data could not allow the computation of profitability indices for some forest stands on site classes 3 and 4 when using EFISCEN database or regional yield functions estimates.

Figure 22 compares the four species' profitability within 16 site conditions. In general, spruce stands were more profitable than other species. However, some exceptions appeared on northern sites with mineral soils where pine was more profitable at higher discount rates. According to the default MOTTI management guidelines, pine was the least profitable on peatlands than any other species.

Figure 22 - The EAE sensitivity of the analysed species to discount rate by ecological factors. Only MOTTI simulations considered for yield estimations.

3.2.3. Spatially explicit profitability indicators for Finnish forests

Each of the 417 unique forest stand addresses (FSAs) defined in section 2.2.2 was joined with the corresponding calculated profitability indices (NPV and EAE). Figure 23 presents the spatial distribution of NPVs across Finnish forests and Figure 24 presents the spread of corresponding EAEs. Note that a positive NPV or EAE indicates a profitable investment and negative values indicate unprofitability (Figure 25).

The impact of the discount rate is very clear (Figure 23 - Figure 25). When using the yield estimations given by both the EFISCEN inventory database and the regional yield functions, all forest stands became unprofitable at a discount rate of five percent. At the same level of discount rate, in the case of MOTTI yield estimations, the profitability was reduced significantly, with the entire northern region becoming unprofitable. However, the profitability of stands in southern region did not fall off, yet yielded minor profits (up to 38 € ha⁻¹year⁻¹).

The northern birch stands observed in Figure 5A had low profitability or were unprofitable (Figure 23 and Figure 24). Specifically, they were profitable only for MOTTI yield estimations.

All in all, there were clear differences between northern and southern regions in terms of profitability. Additionally, at low discount rates there were noticeable differences between stands on mineral soils and stand on peatlands. Generally, forest stands on peatlands were unprofitable.

Figure 23 - Spatial distribution of NPV for Finnish forests.

Figure 24 - Spatial distribution of EAE for Finnish forests.

Figure 25 - Profitability assessment for Finnish forests.

4. Discussions

In this study, a GIS-based approach was used for estimating and mapping the net present values and their equal annual equivalent across Finnish forests at a high spatial resolution (100×100 m). The computation required detailed information on forest stand growth, stand management and economic data (i.e. stumpage prices and management costs). The volume increment at the forest stand level was estimated in three ways: developing regional yield functions, using the EFISCEN inventory database and the MOTTI forest stand simulator.

4.1. Yield estimates, challenges

Computing net present values is not possible without estimating the standing volume at various ages throughout the rotation. Other studies have also underlined the high importance of using growth and yield models mentioning the drawback regarding data availability (e.g. Yemshanov et al. 2007; Chan et al. 2011). However, it is worth mentioning that the task of fitting stand yield models was one of the greatest challenges in this study.

An important limitation when estimating standing volumes with regional yield functions was that reliable models could not be computed for the group of species 'other broad-leaved' for all site conditions (Figure 15). In most cases observations were either completely lacking or their numbers were insufficient to allow fitting models (Appendix 8 - Figure 34 and 35). Other limitations are related to the statistical modelling per se and are discussed below, in section 4.2. The same issue regarding the lack of observations was also encountered for the EFISCEN inventory database.

However, when modelling the stand growth with the MOTTI simulator it was possible to overcome the issue of insufficient data. The MOTTI forest stand simulator has been already used in studies of forest economic indicators across Finland. For example, Hynynen et al. (2005) used the MOTTI simulator to analyse the profitability (NPV) of different management scenarios in several types of spruce stands. Kojola et al. (2012) used MOTTI in a similar manner for Scots pine stands on drained peatlands.

Ahtikoski et al. (2004) simulated the growth of silver birch stands with MOTTI in order to examine the NPV changes under the influence of alternative thinning intensities.

Other forest growth simulators have also been used in studies related to forest stand profitability. For example, in the site conditions of southern Germany, Dieter (2001) simulated the growth of spruce and beech stands with an individual-tree growth model for calculating the land expectation value. To analyse the effects of climate change and management on timber yield and NPV, Garcia-Gonzalo et al. (2007) applied a process-based ecosystem model (FinnFor) for a forest management unit in Finland. Hanewinkel et al. (2010) used the distance-dependent, individual-tree growth simulator SILVA to evaluate the economic effects of a forest biome shift under climate change in southwest Germany.

Generally, the profitability was higher when using the estimates returned by the MOTTI simulator than when using those based on the EFISCEN inventory database or the regional yield functions. Importantly, the differences between the values of the profitability indicators returned by the three yield estimation methods increased with site quality, that is, from peatlands to mineral soils, from site class S4 to S1 and also from north to south for each group of species (Figure 18 - Figure 21). This reflects the high impact of the yield estimation method on the final results, especially on sites of higher quality. These results concerning the variation in profitability are consistent with results from earlier studies. For instance, Holopainen et al. (2010) indicated that around one third of the observed variation in NPV was attributable to errors in growth predictions. They also reported a higher variation of NPVs at low discount rates. Similarly, in the present study the discrepancies between EAEs returned by different yield estimation methods increased with decreasing discount rate (Figure 18 - Figure 21).

4.2. Modelling regional yield functions

Approximately 15.6 million stands dominated by pine, 4.4 with spruce, 3.3 dominated by birch and 0.4 with other broad-leaved tree species were considered for constructing regional yield functions based on the stand conditions at the time of inventory. Imposing conditions regarding the shares of stand volume occupied by the dominant

species and also a canopy cover threshold resulted in a reduction of the above-mentioned figures. These imposed thresholds were needed in order to stratify data into more homogenous layers and reduce the number of extreme values as much as possible. Additionally, these thresholds had to also be within the boundaries of the stand structures and compositions usually observed in situ. This aspect was partially accounted for by choosing flexible thresholds as described in section 2.2.3.

In this study, the logistic and Gompertz sigmoid functions were used to model forest stand growth. In such studies it is common to log-transform the dependent variable. This operation is supposed to ensure a normal error distribution and also homogenize the variance, which sometimes tends to increase with age. However, in this study, the yield functions were fitted directly to the untransformed data of age (independent variable) and standing volume (dependent variable). There were several reasons behind the decision to use untransformed data. First, such linearizing transformations have been reported to lead to numeric problems in case of nonlinear regressions due to the complex error structure (Seber & Wild 2003). Second, maintaining the original scaling of the data was suggested to be more expressive (Seber & Wild 2003). Moreover, back-transforming the predicted yield values to the original scale also introduces a new source of bias into the analysis (Sprugel 1983). Third, it appears that a normal error distribution is not a strong prerequisite for the nonlinear least squares method (Seber & Wild 2003). The other issue concerning heteroscedasticity can be solved using weighted nonlinear least squares techniques (Bates & Watts 1988). All in all, it may be best to avoid transformations (Zuur et al. 2010).

Consequently, in this study no transformations were applied and the estimates for the parameters were obtained with nonlinear least squares techniques. However, these advanced statistical techniques are not a panacea and come with the important cost of complexity. Nonlinear least squares techniques also require initial guesses for the starting parameter values. This can represent a drawback because the convergence algorithms used for computing parameter estimates sometimes fail because of the initial naive guesses. In this study, a solution to this problem was to gradually increase the number of iterations or the convergence tolerance. However, this indeed made convergence possible but with the cost of altering the standard errors of the parameter estimates.

In the case of birch stands on northern site class 1, both on mineral soils and peatlands, certain heavily clustered observations were eliminated. Generally, these stands were characterized by low volumes at old ages, resulting in clusters of extreme values on the volume-age scatter plots. Removing these outlier-values was considered acceptable for the purpose of this study. It is highly probable that these observations belong to a particular species of birch or even aspen, therefore more accurate data based on further stratification should be considered in future studies.

Both considered models (logistic or Gompertz) had significant parameter estimates, yet only one was selected for further inference. The choice was based both on AIC values and visual assessments of over- or under- fitting the data. As Burnham & Anderson (2002) suggest, a model with $\Delta AIC > 10$ has essentially no support for further consideration. In this study, if one of the models had an AIC up to 10 units bigger but obviously fitted the data better, then it was the one considered for further inference. All in all, model selection was not a purely mechanical operation based only on AIC.

4.3. Profitability of forest stands in Finland

This study represents a unique approach for spatially valuating timber provisioning of Finnish forests at a 100×100 m resolution. Two profitability indices (NPV and EAE) were considered in this endeavour. However, other indices can be used in the cost-benefit analysis of investments and further details related to the forestry sector are reviewed by Prokofieva & Thorsen (2011). The reasoning behind choosing the NPV and EAE were provided in the Introduction.

Generally, the results suggest a major influence of the soil type (mineral or peat) on profitability indices, independent of species, discount rates or the method used for yield estimation. Under the tested management guidelines, stands on mineral soils were more profitable than stands on peatlands. Even though not profitable for timber production, stands located on peatlands are still valuable given their capacity of carbon assimilation, their role in biodiversity conservation and through the provision of other ecosystem services. Indeed, peatland ecosystems are regarded as the most efficient carbon sink on

the planet (Hugron et al. 2013). Future research should urgently consider the valuation of such non-timber ecosystem services.

In this study, only a management scenario with no thinnings before the final cutting was considered for the species' groups Scots pine, birch and other broad-leaved on peatlands (Figure 17; Appendix 10). Kojola et al. (2012) suggested that such a 'passive regime' would severely impact the profitability of Scots pine. On peatlands, a management scenario with thinnings was considered only for spruce. Overall, according to the output from the MOTTI simulator, spruce remained the only profitable species on peatlands at a discount rate of one percent (Figure 19). These results suggest a positive impact of thinnings on the profitability of stands on peatlands. Generally, this underlines the high influence of the management scheme on stand profitability. This is an important factor which was tackled by many studies (e.g. Ahtikoski et al. 2004; Hynynen et al. 2005; Yemshanov et al. 2007; Kojola et al. 2012).

The profitability also decreased from south to north. Even if unprofitable peatlands are dominating the north (Figure 4B; Figure 25), the profitability decrease in northern forests was also observed on mineral soils. Whereas the silvicultural costs were slightly lower in the three forestry centres of the northern region, timber prices were slightly lower as well (Appendix 2). The main factor consists probably in the less favourable growing conditions, reflected in lower yield estimates (Figure 17). On the profitability maps the border between south and north appears to be very sharp (Figure 23 - Figure 25). Additionally, the central area of the southern region was the most profitable. This may be, however, relate to the strong presence of Norway spruce in that region (Figure 5A).

The comparison between species (Figure 22) revealed the influence of yield estimates and management on profitability (Figure 17). Overall, spruce was the most profitable species, followed by pine, but only on mineral soils (Figure 22). Moreover, the average stumpage prices were slightly higher for spruce than for pine (Appendix 2). These results are consistent with other valuation studies. For instance, Triviño et al. (2015) found that in the conditions of Central Finland the best stands for providing harvest revenues and carbon services (storage and sequestration) were those dominated by spruce.

The results of the sensitivity analysis regarding the influence of the discount rate on the profitability of each species under 16 different site conditions across Finland could be useful to inform decision makers. Target policies could be related to conservation incentives programs. For instance, Juutinen et al. (2008) suggested that timber value maps can inform policy makers in the process of designating potential conservation areas. For example, policy makers could use the monetary value of the timber as an estimate for the opportunity cost of introducing harvesting restrictions or even stopping management on a particular site. Nevertheless, all forest ecosystem services should be considered in such appraisals. Further arguments are provided in the section 4.5 below.

Despite considering detailed forest stand simulations, current management guidelines, the variation of growth conditions, discount rates and the spatial variation of costs and stumpage prices, the approach proposed in this study has several limitations. For instance, inherent fluctuations of the timber assortment price during a management cycle were not considered. A simple approach to integrate such variability was suggested by Ojea et al. (2012), who make the simplifying assumption that stumpage prices rise annually by a constant rate. However, the impact of price fluctuations on the final profitability results is probably smaller than that of yield estimates (Holopainen et al. 2010). Moreover, Hynynen et al. (2005) showed that changes in future stumpage prices do not significantly alter the financial ranking of alternative management schedules. The approach used in the current study also ignores the possible occurrence of hazards like wind, snow, fire, grazing, insect and fungi, which would imply additional costs. For instance, Dieter (2001) included the impact of storm and insects in his economic simulations. Another concern is related to the possible transfer and applicability of the proposed approach to other conditions than the ones of Finnish forest. Generally, the restricted access to detailed forest growth and economic data represents a serious limitation, an issue already under debate in other studies (e.g. Pearce 2001; Yemshanov et al. 2007; Ojea et al. 2012). Note that in the approach used in this study the cash flows were computed only for pure even-aged stands with a clear cut at the end of the management cycle followed always by an artificial regeneration. All mixed stands were modelled as pure stands dominated by the species with the highest share of standing volume. Such simplifying assumptions were unavoidable considering the complex dynamics of mixed stands and the limited scope of this study. However, considering their growing importance worldwide, an important

goal of future studies should be to integrate complex and more flexible cash flows adapted to mixed stands. It is also worth mentioning that in Finland pure stands⁸ represent around 55% of the total forest land and stands with a low degree of mixing⁹ represent 31% (METLA 2012a).

4.4. The 'sustainable' discount rate

Hepburn & Koundouri (2007) mentioned that there is an important academic debate with respect to choosing the 'right' discount rate. They criticized the fact that this rate is kept constant over time and recommended using a declining one due to the uncertainty of future economic conditions. They showed that differences in computing NPV based on constant discount rates and computing NPV based on declining discount rates are significant. The highest impact is on long forest management cycles for which the NPV can be negative for constant discount rates, making long term investments not profitable and therefore posing threats to sustainability. The results of this study are consistent with such critics. For instance, the default MOTTI management scenario for pine stands on peatlands suggests a higher age for the final cut than for any other species (Figure 17 or Appendix 10). However, pine stands are the worst in terms of profitability on southern peatlands and it gets worse at higher constant discount rates. Moreover, the lack of thinning aggravates the situation, as already discussed.

As a result of this debate, many authors embraced the approach of running a sensitivity analysis, that is, calculations are done for several discount rates. The Eurostat pilot programme in forest accounting suggested a range between 0.5 and 3.5% for European forests (Eurostat 2000). In the most recent appraisal guide, the European Commission suggested a range between 2.8 and 7.7% for the social discount rate within the EU member states with the specification that 'France, Germany and the UK have autonomously adopted values for their national projects' (Table B.2, EC 2008 p. 209). It is reasoned that considering higher discount rates should result in a better evaluation of competing investments (EC 2008; Prokofieva & Thorsen 2011). However, for forest investments it has been observed that high and constant discount rates tend to reduce

⁸ Dominant species' share of stand total volume is over 95%.

⁹ Dominant species' share of stand total volume is between 75 and 95%.

the incentives for long term investments, resulting in lower harvesting ages, which in turn contradicts the sustainable forest management concept (Hepburn & Koundouri 2007; Ojea et al. 2012).

4.5. Further valuating other ecosystem services

The present thesis focuses only on the economic valuation and mapping the economic value of *timber provisioning*. Even though it is easier to value timber provision, other forest ecosystem services need to be considered because all ecological functions of forests are equally economic functions (Pearce 2001). Furthermore, many authors underlined the fact that numerous goods and services remain unvalued and ignored in economic decision-making (e.g. Costanza et al. 1997; Navrud & Pruckner 1997; Krieger 2001; Pearce 2001; Bateman et al. 2003; Maes et al. 2012; Snowdon & Harou 2013). However, valuating such goods and services is a very challenging task. On the one hand, because it requires very good knowledge and understanding of ecosystem services (Troy & Wilson 2006). On the other hand, because their benefits often returns almost entirely to local communities, making it hard to quantify their value in economic units per hectare (Pearce 2001). This also offers a justification for policies that conserve local forests ecosystems to better focus on the local context and values (Ninan & Inoue 2013). However, as discussed by Costanza et al. (1997), ecosystem services can also be considered to have an infinite value to humankind, rendering their valuation to a superfluous act. All in all, further research needs to address the complex issue of valuating and mapping the economic value of other forest ecosystem services (e.g. Häyhä et al. 2015).

5. Conclusions

The EU 2020 Biodiversity Strategy, besides requiring mapping and assessing the state of ecosystems and their services, also underlines the importance of assessing the economic value of ecosystem services. In this context, mapping the value of forests conveys information that can be used for communication and decision-making. To the best of the author's knowledge, the approach presented in this study represents one of the first attempts to produce forest profitability maps with a high spatial resolution (100×100 m) based on yield estimations and local management guidelines.

The proposed approach required considerable programming and computing effort, as well as large amounts of data for modelling forest stand yields. The choice of the method for estimating the yields had a significant impact on the profitability indicators, particularly at low discount rates and on fertile sites. Within the considered range of management strategies, growth conditions and discount rates, Norway spruce stands were generally the most profitable. As expected, stands on mineral soils were more profitable than stands on peatlands. However, the low profitability or unprofitability of the pure stands of Scots pine, birch or other broad-leaved species on peatlands might have been exacerbated by the absence of benefits from thinnings.

Mapping the economic value of timber provisioning has great potential to assist policy-making. For example, policies related to carbon sequestration, conservation incentives programs or setting investment priorities would greatly benefit from using such information. Policy makers could better assess the opportunity costs of areas targeted for conservation. Even though it is easier to value timber provisioning, other forest ecosystem services could be considered for future appraisals. Considering the novelty of the methods described in this study, it will hopefully inspire other studies and help further the quickly expanding field of forest valuation and profitability mapping.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. Extracts from metadata of MS-NFI 2011

Extract regarding the theme 'Total volume':

'The volume of a tree is defined as the volume of the stem wood above stump until the top of the tree. [...]. The unit and class interval of the volume is 1 m³/ha [...].'

Extract regarding the theme 'Canopy cover':

'The canopy cover of trees is the vertical projection area on the horizontal plane of the canopies of the individual trees on a field plot (without double counting the overlapping canopies). In NFI10, it was assessed in the field as a shares (0-99%) on a fixed radius plot. For the NFI11 plots, it was estimated using k-NN method and the NFI10 plot data. [...] The canopy cover proportion of broad-leaved trees is derived from the total cover using the volume of the growing stock. However, in the seedling stands, the canopy cover of broad leaved trees is assessed using the shares of the stem numbers.'

Extract regarding the theme 'Age':

'The age of the growing stock on a forest stand is the weighted average of the trees, the basal area of the tree as the weight. The age is assessed in the field for the field plot stands on forest land and poorly productive forest land in the classes of one year.'

Appendix 2. Unit costs and average stumpage prices

Table 10 - Unit costs of silvicultural and forest improvement work, 2010 (€/ha).

A = Non-industrial, private, etc.; B = Forest industries and state

Forestry centre	Clearing of regeneration areas		Disc trenching		Mounding		Planting		Improvement of young stands	
	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B	A	B
<i>Whole country</i>	157	128	168	162	317	304	692	630	359	477
0 Ahvenanmaa	-	-	-	-	261	-	925	-	295	-
1 Rannikko	163	117	167	200	347	324	712	615	373	510
2 Lounais-Suomi	160	138	184	196	344	352	715	653	406	524
3 Häme-Uusimaa	189	161	203	214	334	381	785	714	388	515
4 Kaakkois-Suomi	195	126	220	187	341	320	618	638	295	495
5 Pirkanmaa	223	171	193	206	312	373	719	764	390	519
6 Etelä-Savo	193	113	175	206	318	339	707	649	344	478
7 Etelä-Pohjanmaa	173	121	172	145	321	342	676	616	407	501
8 Keski-Suomi	159	166	185	215	321	360	698	679	297	506
9 Pohjois-Savo	270	129	156	197	314	327	735	633	365	451
10 Pohjois-Karjala	-	129	-	218	-	322	-	604	-	430
11 Kainuu	195	106	141	149	302	307	633	671	251	481
12 Pohjois-Pohjanmaa	93	125	165	143	274	280	550	584	380	500
13 Lappi	89	131	148	160	311	237	651	581	358	454

Source: Finnish statistical yearbook of forestry (Ylitalo 2011)

Table 11 - Average stumpage prices in non-industrial, private forests by forestry centre, 2010 (€/m³)

Forestry centre	Logs			Pulpwood		
	Pine	Spruce	Birch	Pine	Spruce	Birch
<i>Whole country</i>	54.03	55.17	39.43	15.52	18.61	15.45
0 Ahvenanmaa	35.22	34.35	28.14	11.04	13.18	8.77
1 Rannikko	54.55	54.89	38.39	15.49	19.37	15.45
2 Lounais-Suomi	55.33	56.20	35.81	15.73	19.76	15.35
3 Häme-Uusimaa	54.70	55.63	39.55	14.66	19.26	15.00
4 Kaakkois-Suomi	54.29	55.19	39.16	15.19	18.72	14.66
5 Pirkanmaa	54.59	55.83	37.99	15.30	19.44	15.25
6 Etelä-Savo	53.77	53.99	40.51	14.75	17.86	14.74
7 Etelä-Pohjanmaa	54.42	55.97	37.34	16.03	19.06	16.34
8 Keski-Suomi	53.54	55.12	39.93	15.00	18.31	15.24
9 Pohjois-Savo	53.67	55.37	38.91	14.89	17.74	15.21
10 Pohjois-Karjala	55.18	56.15	40.16	15.81	18.04	14.94
11 Kainuu	55.32	54.25	36.61	16.53	18.93	15.80
12 Pohjois-Pohjanmaa	53.31	53.35	37.16	16.35	18.69	16.65
13 Lappi	49.34	48.55	-	16.08	19.42	15.80

Source: Finnish statistical yearbook of forestry (Ylitalo 2011)

Appendix 3. Geoprocessing the NUTS 2010 dataset

Table 12 - Aggregation of NUTS 2010 units into forestry centres - correspondence between forestry centres and NUTS 2010 codes

Forestry centre	NUTS 2010 code
0 Ahvenanmaa	FI200
1 Rannikko	FI195; F1B1
2 Lounais-Suomi	FI196; FI1C1
3 Häme-Uusimaa	FI1C2; FI1C3
4 Kaakkois-Suomi	FI1C5; FI1C4
5 Pirkanmaa	FI197
6 Etelä-Savo	FI1D1
7 Etelä-Pohjanmaa	FI194; FI1D5
8 Keski-Suomi	FI193
9 Pohjois-Savo	FI1D2
10 Pohjois-Karjala	FI1D3
11 Kainuu	FI1D4
12 Pohjois-Pohjanmaa	FI1D6
13 Lappi	FI1D7

Displacement adjustment with the 'Shift' tool:

In the case of the raster dataset depicting northern and southern Finland, the X coordinates were shifted by -25.3525 m and the Y coordinates by -35.8734 m. For the raster dataset depicting the 14 forestry centres, the X coordinates had to be shifted by -11.3605402 m and the Y coordinates by -29.21625 m.

Appendix 4. Geoprocessing the soil raster dataset

Displacement adjustment with the 'Shift' tool:

The software required precise number of digit after decimal point: X coordinates were shifted by 13.8471929 m and Y coordinates by -45.85521 m.

Filling the mismatching gaps with estimated neighboring soil values:

The 'Focal Statistics' tool was applied, computing the 'majority' statistics within a 11 km radius circle neighborhood around each water body cell. The 'majority' statistics type computes the most frequent value of the cells within the neighborhood area. A mismatching example is given below in Figure 26.

Figure 26 - Overlapping imperfections between MS-NFI and soil raster datasets. The MS-NFI datasets have a spatial resolution of 100×100 m and the soil is given at 1×1 km.

The procedure involved the separation of all null values (includes water bodies) as polygons (Figure 27A) and then computing their area and perimeter. The next step was computing the radius that satisfied the corresponding circle of given area and given perimeter of each polygon.

First step was to transform all null pixel values to zero and this was done by using the 'Raster Calculator' with the expression $Con(IsNull("Soil_raster"), 0, "Soil_raster")$. Then all zero values were extracted as a separate raster dataset by using the 'Extract by Attributes' tool with the expression $Value = 0$. Further, the raster dataset was transformed to a polygon feature dataset using the 'Raster to Polygon' tool. The attribute table of the new feature was exported as *.csv file and processed in Excel and the radiuses were computed as mentioned above. For each polygon of area (A) and perimeter (P), the radius that satisfies the circle of given area A and given perimeter P is $R=2A/P$. The maximum radius was around 5.5 km and its double size of 11 km was considered for computing in 'Focal Statistics'.

Further, the 'Focal Statistics' raster output (hereafter: *soil_FS_rst*) was resampled from 1×1 km to 100×100 m resolution. Then a 'Raster Calculator' conditional statement was used to replace the water bodies values of the initial soil raster dataset (hereafter: *soil_gaps_rst*) with the values derived from the neighboring cell values (from *soil_FS_rst* - Figure 27B). The conditional statement used was $Con(IsNull("soil_gaps_rst"), "soil_FS_rst", "soil_gaps_rst")$.

Figure 27 - Intermediate raster datasets for filling the soil gaps. A) Null values and water bodies; B) Soil classes after applying the 'Focal Statistics' tool.

Appendix 5. Python script for defining dominant species stands

```
# Import required libraries and modules
import arcpy
import os
import numpy
from arcpy import env
from arcpy.sa import *
# Set environment settings (provide path to the workspace - geodatabase)
env.workspace = "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb"
# Set local variables (the total volume raster datasets)
spruce = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VTotRealSpruce1ha')
pine = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VTotRealPine1ha')
birch = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VTotRealBirch1ha')
othersp = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VTotRealOtherSp1ha')
# Create a list with the above local variables (raster datasets)
# - takes all raster datasets from geodatabase (which was set in env.workspace) which
start with 'VTotReal'
rstlist = arcpy.ListRasters("VTotReal*", "All")
# Compute maximum pixel value from the list 'rstlist'
maxrst = CellStatistics(rstlist, "MAXIMUM", "DATA")
# Save the result raster with changing the pixel depth for optimal memory usage
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(maxrst, "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\MaxVol",
"DEFAULTS", "0", "", "", "", "16_BIT_UNSIGNED")
# Attribute the saved raster to a variable (maxrst)
maxrst = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\MaxVol')
# Using the conditional function ('con'): if maximum volume equals given species total
volume, then return corresponding species code; otherwise NoData will be returned. The
commands will output raster datasets for each dominant species.
arcpy.CopyRaster_management((Con((spruce - maxrst) == 0, 1)),
"F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\LogicDominSpruce1ha",
"DEFAULTS",
"0", "", "", "", "16_BIT_UNSIGNED")
```

```
arcpy.CopyRaster_management((Con((pine - maxrst) == 0, 10)),
    "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\LogicDominPinelha",
    "0","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED"), "DEFAULTS",
arcpy.CopyRaster_management((Con((birch - maxrst) == 0, 100)),
    "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\LogicDominBirchlha",
    "0","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED"), "DEFAULTS",
arcpy.CopyRaster_management((Con((othersp - maxrst) == 0, 1000)),
    "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\LogicDominOtherSplha",
    "0","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED"), "DEFAULTS",
# Create a list with the dominant species raster datasets (previously defined)
# - takes all raster datasets from geodatabase which start with ' LogicDomin'
rstlistLogic = arcpy.ListRasters("LogicDomin*", "All")
# Sum up the cell values (containing species codes)
LogicSum = CellStatistics(rstlistLogic, "SUM", "DATA")
# Save the sum raster dataset
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(LogicSum,
    "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\LogicSumVol",
    "0","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED"), "DEFAULTS",
# A reclassification was done using Reclassify tool (not used as script but in the GUI)
# - raster LogicSumVol becomes LogicSumVol4Sp
# - reclassification tackled those stands were more than one species was dominant
# (species having same maximum standing volume)
# 11=1 (pine & spruce becomes spruce stand),
# 101=100 (birch & spruce becomes birch stand),
# 110=100 (birch & pine becomes birch stand),
# 111=100 (birch & pine & spruce becomes birch stand),
# 1001=1000 (other broad-leaved & spruce becomes other broad-leaved stand),
# 1010=1000 (other broad-leaved & pine becomes other broad-leaved stand),
# 1011=1000 (other broad-leaved & pine & spruce becomes other broad-leaved stand),
# 1100=100 (other broad-leaved & birch becomes birch stand),
# 1101=100 (other broad-leaved & birch & spruce becomes birch stand),
# 1110=100 (other broad-leaved & birch & pine becomes birch stand),
# 1111=100 (other broad-leaved & birch & pine & spruce becomes birch stand)
# Attribute the reclassification raster previously created to a variable (LogicSum)
LogicSum = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\LogicSumVol4Sp')
# Assign final codes:
#1 - birch #2 - pine #3 - spruce #4 - other broad-leaved
arcpy.CopyRaster_management((Con(LogicSum==1, 3, Con(LogicSum==10, 2, Con(LogicSum==100,
1, Con(LogicSum==1000, 4))))), "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\Species_code",
"DEFAULTS", "0","","","8_BIT_UNSIGNED")
```

Appendix 6. Python script for selecting stands with a certain volume proportional share of the dominant species

```
# The script will sum up all species by total volume. Then compares the ratio between
# species volume and the summed volume with a certain threshold. If the ratio is above
# the threshold then the forest stand is selected.
# Import required libraries and modules
import arcpy
import os
import numpy
from arcpy import env
from arcpy.sa import *
# Set environment settings (provide path to the workspace - geodatabase)
env.workspace = "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb"
# Set local variables
spruce = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VTotRealSpruce1ha')
pine = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VTotRealPinelha')
birch = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VTotRealBirchlha')
othersp = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VTotRealOtherSplha')
# Create a list with the above local variables (raster datasets)
# - takes all raster datasets from geodatabase (which was set in env.workspace) which
# start with 'VTotReal'
rstlist = arcpy.ListRasters("VTotReal*", "All")
# Sum up the total volume of all species
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(CellStatistics(rstlist,
    "SUM", "DATA"),
    "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VolSumAllSp",
    "0","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED")
# Attribute the summation volume raster to a variable (SumVol)
SumVol = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VolSumAllSp')
# Transform the summation raster dataset from 32 bit to 16 bit pixel depth (for memory
# usage)
```

```
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(SumVol, "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finland.gdb\SumVol",  
"DEFAULTS", "0","","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED")  
# Assign value 1 to NoData in SumVol raster dataset  
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(Con(IsNull(SumVol), 1, SumVol),  
"F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finland.gdb\SumVol_1ND", "DEFAULTS",  
"0","","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED")  
# Overwrite SumVol raster dataset with the output raster of previous command  
SumVol = arcpy.Raster('F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finland.gdb\SumVol_1ND')  
# At cell level if sum of volumes is different from 1 (representing NoData) then divide  
species volume by sum volume. 'Divide' function was used in order to have real number  
division (otherwise is truncated). If the ratio is above a certain threshold then  
retrieve the pixel value (volume) otherwise NoData will be attributed by default.  
# Depending on the value of the threshold the following type of stands were considered:  
pure (95%), stand with some mixing (75%), mixed stands (50%)  
# For Scots pine on sites 1, 2 and 3 the proportional share of the dominant species of  
the volume was set to over 95%, consequently defining pure stands  
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(Con(SumVol != 1, Con(Divide(Float(pine),Float(SumVol)) >=  
Float(0.95), pine)), "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VolPurePine", "DEFAULTS",  
"0","","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED")  
# For Scots pine on some sites 4, due to reduced number of stands, the threshold of 75%  
was used for defining stand with some mixing  
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(Con(SumVol != 1, Con(Divide(Float(pine),Float(SumVol)) >=  
Float(0.75), pine)), "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VolPurePine_75", "DEFAULTS",  
"0","","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED")  
# For Norway spruce on sites 1, 2 and 3, the threshold of 75% was used for defining  
stand with some mixing  
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(Con(SumVol != 1, Con(Divide(Float(spruce),Float(SumVol)) >=  
Float(0.75), spruce)), "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VolPureSpruce_75",  
"DEFAULTS", "0","","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED")  
# For Norway spruce on sites 4, due to reduced number of stands, the threshold of 50%  
was used for defining mixed stands  
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(Con(SumVol != 1, Con(Divide(Float(spruce),Float(SumVol)) >=  
Float(0.50), spruce)), "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VolPureSpruce_50",  
"DEFAULTS", "0","","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED")  
# For birch on all four sites the threshold of 75% was used for defining stand with some  
mixing  
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(Con(SumVol != 1, Con(Divide(Float(birch),Float(SumVol)) >=  
Float(0.75), birch)), "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VolPureBirch_75",  
"DEFAULTS", "0","","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED")  
# For other broad-leaved species on sites class 1 and some sites class 2 the threshold  
of 75% was used for defining stand with some mixing  
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(Con(SumVol != 1, Con(Divide(Float(othersp),Float(SumVol)) >=  
Float(0.75), othersp)), "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VolPureOtherSp_75",  
"DEFAULTS", "0","","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED")  
# For other broad-leaved species on some sites class 2, sites class 3 and 4 the  
threshold of 50% was used for defining mixed stands  
arcpy.CopyRaster_management(Con(SumVol != 1, Con(Divide(Float(othersp),Float(SumVol)) >=  
Float(0.50), othersp)), "F:\EFI\Server\Finland\Finlandlha.gdb\VolPureOtherSp_50",  
"DEFAULTS", "0","","","","16_BIT_UNSIGNED")
```

Appendix 7. R script for nonlinear yield functions modelling

```
# Get the path of the txt file that contains the tabulation of volume by age. The file  
represents the output of Tabulate Area (Spatial Analyst) tool from ArcGis  
path <- file.choose()  
# Read the content of the txt file  
data <- read.table(file=path, dec=".", sep="," , header=T)  
# Check for type of format  
str(data)  
# Convert factor to numeric for convenience considering that comma is used as thousands  
separator within the factor  
data <- sapply(data, function(f) {as.numeric(gsub(",","", as.character(f)))})  
# Convert back from matrix to data frame (previous sapply function creates matrices)  
data <- data.frame(data)  
# Obtain the number of pixels (frequencies) by dividing with 10 000 m2 (100*100 m2)  
# the columns OBJECTID & VALUE should not be affected by the operation, therefore they  
are saved separately  
objectid <- data$OBJECTID  
value <- data$VALUE  
data <- round(data/(100*100))  
data$OBJECTID <- objectid  
data$VALUE <- value  
# Transform the original contingency table to frequency table  
# import required libraries (packages)
```

```
library(data.table)
library(stringr)
library(reshape2)
# convert data frame to data table
mydata <- as.data.table(melt(data, na.rm=T, id=c("OBJECTID", "VALUE"),
variable.name="Vol", value.name="Count"))
# convert string to numeric for convenience
mydata[,Vol := as.numeric(str_sub(Vol, start=7, end=9))]
# order by VALUE and Vol columns
setkey(mydata, OBJECTID, Vol)
# generate an index column (key)
mydata[, num := 1:.N]
mydata <- mydata[rep(num, Count)]
Ytbl <- mydata[,list(OBJECTID, VALUE, Vol)]
setnames(Ytbl, "VALUE", "Age")
# -----
# Nonlinear regression
# Import required libraries (packages)
library("nls2")
# Plot the cloud of points corresponding to the volume - age pairs
windows(record=T)
plot(Ytbl$Vol~Ytbl$Age, xlab="Age", ylab="Vol")
# -----
# Logistic model
# Self starting Logistic model
# -----
logistic.nls <- nls(Vol ~ SSlogis(Age, Asym, xmid, scal), data=Ytbl)
# when convergence problems occur then try to adjust some convergence factors
logistic.nls <- nls(Vol ~ SSlogis(Age, Asym, xmid, scal), data=Ytbl,
control=nls.control(tol=0.1))
# display the regression's summaries
summary(logistic.nls)
# test if residuals are normally distributed (Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test)
ks.test(residuals(logistic.nls, type="pearson"), "pnorm")
# test if the average of the residual is statistically different from zero
t.test(residuals(logistic.nls, type="pearson"))
# display the nonlinear model
dummy.age <- with(Ytbl, seq(1, 100,1))
lines(dummy.age, predict(logistic.nls, newdata=data.frame(Age=dummy.age)), col="red",
lwd=2)
# Logistic model with starting values
# -----
equation <- Vol ~ Asym/(1+exp((xmid-Age)/scal))
start.values <- data.frame(Asym = c(20,40), xmid = c(15,30), scal = c(1,6))
# search for an approximate model with starting values
model.trial <- nls2(equation, start=start.values, data=Ytbl,
algorithm="random-search", control=nls.control(maxiter = 100))
# use the best guessed starting values to attempt fitting a model to the data
logistic.nls2 <- nls2(equation, start=model.trial, data=Ytbl)
# when convergence problems occur then try to adjust some convergence factors
logistic.nls2 <- nls2(equation, start=model.trial, data=Ytbl,
control=nls.control(tol=0.5))
# display the regression's summaries
summary(logistic.nls2)
# test if residuals are normally distributed (Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test)
ks.test(residuals(logistic.nls2, type="pearson"), "pnorm")
# test if the average of the residual is statistically different from zero
t.test(residuals(logistic.nls2, type="pearson"))
# display the nonlinear model
dummy.age <- with(Ytbl, seq(1, 100,1))
lines(dummy.age, predict(logistic.nls2, newdata=data.frame(Age=dummy.age)), col="red",
lwd=2)
# -----
# Gompertz model
# Self starting Gompertz model
# -----
gompertz.nls <- nls(Vol ~ SSGompertz(Age, Asym, b2, b3), data=Ytbl)
# when convergence problems occur then try to adjust some convergence factors
gompertz.nls <- nls(Vol ~ SSGompertz(Age, Asym, b2, b3), data=Ytbl,
control=nls.control(tol=0.1))
# display the regression's summaries
summary(gompertz.nls)
# test if residuals are normally distributed (Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test)
ks.test(residuals(gompertz.nls, type="pearson"), "pnorm")
# test if the average of the residual is statistically different from zero
t.test(residuals(gompertz.nls, type="pearson"))
```

```
# display the nonlinear model
dummy.age <- with(Ytbl, seq(1, 100,1))
lines(dummy.age, predict(gompertz.nls, newdata=data.frame(Age=dummy.age)), col="green",
lwd=2)
# Gompertz model with starting values
# -----
equation2 <- Vol ~ Asym*exp(-b2*b3^Age)
# starting values should be adjusted accordingly
start.values <- data.frame(Asym = c(70,90), b2 = c(3,10), b3 = c(0.9,1))
# search for an approximate model with starting values
model.trial <- nls2(equation2, start=start.values, data=Ytbl,
algorithm="random-search", control=nls.control(maxiter = 100))
# use the best guessed starting values to attempt fitting a model to the data
gompertz.nls2 <- nls2(equation2, start=model.trial, data=Ytbl)
# when convergence problems occur then try to adjust some convergence factors
gompertz.nls2 <- nls2(equation2, start=model.trial, data=Ytbl,
control=nls.control(tol=0.5))
# display the regression's summaries
summary(gompertz.nls2)
# test if residuals are normally distributed (Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test)
ks.test(residuals(gompertz.nls2, type="pearson"), "pnorm")
# test if the average of the residual is statistically different from zero
t.test(residuals(gompertz.nls2, type="pearson"))
# display the nonlinear model
dummy.age <- with(Ytbl, seq(1, 100,1))
lines(dummy.age, predict(gompertz.nls2, newdata=data.frame(Age=dummy.age)), col="green",
lwd=2)
# -----
# Compare models using AIC
AIC(gompertz.nls, logistic.nls)
# compute AIC difference
AIC(logistic.nls) - AIC(gompertz.nls)
# Extract the RMSEs of the models
summary(gompertz.nls)$sigma
summary(logistic.nls)$sigma
# -----
# Create the final yield table
# choose the desired model
vol.tbl <- predict(gompertz.nls, newdata=data.frame(Age=dummy.age))
YtblFinal <- data.frame(dummy.age, vol.tbl)
# save the table as TAB delimited *.txt file
write.table(YtblFinal, "D:/R/Yield/Table.txt", sep="\t")
# save the coefficients of the Logistic and Gompertz models on the storage device
```

Appendix 8. Regional yield curves

Figure 28 - Yield curves for Scots pine in northern region. NOTE: The first percent value represents dominant species' share of stand total volume. The second percent value represents the minimum canopy cover of the stands analysed for building the yield curve (corresponds to the third quartile of the canopy cover distribution). Age is expressed in years and standing volume ('Vol') in m³/ha. Logistic model is represented by the red line and Gompertz model by the green line.

Figure 29 - Yield curves for Scots pine in southern region. NOTE: The first percent value represents dominant species' share of stand total volume. The second percent value represents the minimum canopy cover of the stands analysed for building the yield curve (corresponds to the third quartile of the canopy cover distribution). Age is expressed in years and standing volume ('Vol') in m³/ha. Logistic model is represented by the red line and Gompertz model by the green line.

Figure 30 - Yield curves for Norway spruce in northern region. NOTE: The first percent value represents dominant species' share of stand total volume. The second percent value represents the minimum canopy cover of the stands analysed for building the yield curve (usually corresponds to the third quartile of the canopy cover distribution, or to the median [m] if there were not enough stands to cover all age classes). Age is expressed in years and standing volume ('Vol') in m³/ha. Logistic model is represented by the red line and Gompertz model by the green line.

Figure 31 - Yield curves for Norway spruce in southern region. NOTE: The first percent value represents dominant species' share of stand total volume. The second percent value represents the minimum canopy cover of the stands analysed for building the yield curve (usually corresponds to the third quartile of the canopy cover distribution, or to a tested minimum value [*] if there were not enough stands to cover all age classes). Age is expressed in years and standing volume ('Vol') in m³/ha. Logistic model is represented by the red line and Gompertz model by the green line.

Figure 32 - Yield curves for birch in northern region. NOTE: The first percent value represents dominant species' share of stand total volume. The second percent value represents the minimum canopy cover of the stands analysed for building the yield curve (corresponds to the third quartile of the canopy cover distribution). Age is expressed in years and standing volume ("Vol") in m³/ha. Logistic model is represented by the red line and Gompertz model by the green line.

Figure 33 - Yield curves for birch in southern region. NOTE: The first percent value represents dominant species' share of stand total volume. The second percent value represents the minimum canopy cover of the stands analysed for building the yield curve (corresponds to the third quartile of the canopy cover distribution). Age is expressed in years and standing volume ('Vol') in m³/ha. Logistic model is represented by the red line and Gompertz model by the green line.

Figure 34 - Yield curves for other broad-leaved species in northern region. NOTE: The first percent value represents dominant species' share of stand total volume. The second percent value represents the minimum canopy cover of the stands analysed for building the yield curve (usually corresponds to the third quartile of the canopy cover distribution, or to the median [m] or 1st quartile [q1] if there were not enough stands to cover all age classes). Age is expressed in years and standing volume ('Vol') in m³/ha. Logistic model is represented by the red line and Gompertz model by the green line.

Figure 35 - Yield curves for broad-leaved species in southern region. NOTE: The first percent value represents dominant species' share of stand total volume. The second percent value represents the minimum canopy cover of the stands analysed for building the yield curve (usually corresponds to the third quartile of the canopy cover distribution, or to the median [m] if there were not enough stands to cover all age classes). Age is expressed in years and standing volume ('Vol') in m³/ha. Logistic model is represented by the red line and Gompertz model by the green line.

Appendix 9. Significant parameter estimates of regional yield functions

No.	Species	Region	Soil	Site	Selected model	Coefficient estimates			Standard error		
						Asym	coef1	coef2	Asym	coef1	coef2
1	Pine	North	mineral	1	Gompertz	109.978	4.160	0.946	0.134	0.079	0.0005
2	Pine	North	mineral	2	Logistic	106.369	51.611	17.806	2.417	0.935	1.184
3	Pine	North	mineral	3	Logistic	105.181	45.778	15.715	0.360	0.211	0.290
4	Pine	North	mineral	4	Logistic	27.102	17.222	4.288	0.547	0.948	0.805
5	Pine	North	peat	1	Gompertz	118.277	2.383	0.961	0.250	0.040	0.0004
6	Pine	North	peat	2	Logistic	86.773	43.679	12.605	1.311	0.801	1.005
7	Pine	North	peat	3	Logistic	81.218	42.813	12.245	0.187	0.202	0.203
8	Pine	North	peat	4	Logistic	25.393	15.326	4.215	0.248	0.439	0.404
9	Pine	South	mineral	1	Gompertz	145.616	3.492	0.945	0.300	0.079	0.001
10	Pine	South	mineral	2	Logistic	128.256	43.747	20.696	1.949	0.742	1.078
11	Pine	South	mineral	3	Gompertz	136.682	8.245	0.930	0.321	0.766	0.002
12	Pine	South	mineral	4	Gompertz	122.308	3.418	0.963	16.946	0.200	0.005
13	Pine	South	peat	1	Gompertz	145.085	3.905	0.939	0.406	0.170	0.001
14	Pine	South	peat	2	Gompertz	130.416	3.312	0.964	4.622	0.618	0.005
15	Pine	South	peat	3	Gompertz	130.431	5.723	0.947	0.663	0.582	0.002
16	Pine	South	peat	4	Gompertz	87.690	3.656	0.960	29.777	0.614	0.015
17	Spruce	North	mineral	1	Logistic	131.146	40.721	8.241	0.296	0.608	0.496
18	Spruce	North	mineral	2	Gompertz	115.784	2.859	0.951	1.038	1.143	0.007
19	Spruce	North	mineral	3	Gompertz	72.974	2.257	0.991	18.260	0.170	0.002
20	Spruce	North	mineral	4	Logistic	46.912	35.082	9.026	2.900	3.464	3.721
21	Spruce	North	peat	1	Logistic	125.953	50.051	16.082	0.418	1.056	0.854
22	Spruce	North	peat	2	Gompertz	124.291	2.447	0.970	2.177	0.915	0.005
23	Spruce	North	peat	3	Gompertz	65.750	3.427	0.984	8.847	0.381	0.003
24	Spruce	North	peat	4	Logistic	45.430	39.510	9.093	1.613	1.524	1.557
25	Spruce	South	mineral	1	Gompertz	270.669	3.892	0.949	0.270	0.044	0.0003
26	Spruce	South	mineral	2	Logistic	225.027	35.687	10.058	0.712	0.420	0.416
27	Spruce	South	mineral	3	Logistic	86.183	21.357	5.053	3.106	3.101	2.478
28	Spruce	South	mineral	4	Gompertz	99.677	4.265	0.934	2.518	1.160	0.012
29	Spruce	South	peat	1	Gompertz	255.329	4.696	0.943	0.800	0.246	0.001
30	Spruce	South	peat	2	Gompertz	210.637	4.744	0.951	1.526	0.760	0.003
31	Spruce	South	peat	3	Logistic	103.864	38.395	14.935	12.227	6.222	5.644
32	Spruce	South	peat	4	Gompertz	104.419	3.265	0.960	6.961	0.778	0.008
33	Birch	North	mineral	1	Gompertz	135.487	2.500	0.966	3.201	0.043	0.001
34	Birch	North	mineral	2	Gompertz	135.583	1.772	0.969	6.134	0.099	0.003
35	Birch	North	mineral	3	Gompertz	94.603	3.442	0.945	1.886	0.459	0.004
36	Birch	North	mineral	4	Logistic	48.935	20.731	14.632	9.422	5.991	5.296
37	Birch	North	peat	1	Gompertz	86.527	3.402	0.937	1.504	0.279	0.004
38	Birch	North	peat	2	Gompertz	92.613	5.885	0.917	0.962	1.043	0.006
39	Birch	North	peat	3	Gompertz	70.416	4.835	0.918	0.809	1.031	0.007
40	Birch	North	peat	4	Logistic	38.079	15.290	5.129	1.823	1.978	2.081
41	Birch	South	mineral	1	Gompertz	138.610	3.420	0.933	0.769	0.056	0.001
42	Birch	South	mineral	2	Gompertz	118.264	3.099	0.937	1.353	0.185	0.003
43	Birch	South	mineral	3	Gompertz	94.018	3.498	0.920	1.286	0.691	0.007
44	Birch	South	mineral	4	Logistic	37.640	7.855	2.598	2.217	0.736	0.761
45	Birch	South	peat	1	Gompertz	115.121	3.576	0.923	1.768	0.267	0.004
46	Birch	South	peat	2	Gompertz	135.338	2.058	0.961	8.021	0.219	0.006
47	Birch	South	peat	3	Gompertz	92.178	6.480	0.902	1.819	2.252	0.013
48	Birch	South	peat	4	Logistic	30.062	6.575	1.985	2.254	1.033	0.943
49	Other	North	mineral	1	Gompertz	86.223	5.482	0.888	3.345	0.504	0.008
50	Other	North	mineral	2	Gompertz	52.852	5.232	0.877	1.836	2.440	0.023
51	Other	North	mineral	3	Gompertz	94.603	3.442	0.945	1.886	0.459	0.004
52	Other	North	mineral	4	Logistic	48.935	20.731	14.632	9.422	5.991	5.296
53	Other	North	peat	1	Gompertz	38.452	4.942	0.855	1.416	0.752	0.013
54	Other	North	peat	2	Logistic	92.613	5.885	0.917	0.962	1.043	0.006
55	Other	North	peat	3	Gompertz	70.416	4.835	0.918	0.809	1.031	0.007
56	Other	North	peat	4	Logistic	38.079	15.290	5.129	1.823	1.978	2.081
57	Other	South	mineral	1	Logistic	154.395	19.594	5.573	1.228	0.158	0.169
58	Other	South	mineral	2	Gompertz	127.651	4.590	0.935	32.161	1.526	0.023
59	Other	South	mineral	3	Gompertz	94.018	3.498	0.920	1.286	0.691	0.007
60	Other	South	mineral	4	Logistic	37.640	7.855	2.598	2.217	0.736	0.761
61	Other	South	peat	1	Logistic	194.547	24.930	6.893	8.783	0.892	0.522
62	Other	South	peat	2	Gompertz	102.741	9.716	0.892	14.890	3.602	0.022
63	Other	South	peat	3	Gompertz	92.178	6.480	0.902	1.819	2.252	0.013
64	Other	South	peat	4	Logistic	30.062	6.575	1.985	2.254	1.033	0.943

NOTE: *coef1* is *xmid* for logistic (Eq.1) or *b2* for Gompertz model (Eq.2); *coef2* is *scal* for logistic or *b3* for Gompertz model

Appendix 9. Continued

No.	Species	t - value			AIC (for model selection)			RMSE (for model selection)		
		Asym	coef1	coef2	Gompertz	Logistic	Dif.	Gompertz	Logistic	Dif.
1	Pine	820.1	52.9	2101.4	2693236	2693408	172	31.182	31.192	0.010
2	Pine	44.0	55.2	15.0	38962	38948	-13	30.327	30.276	-0.051
3	Pine	292.3	217.0	54.2	799469	799442	-27	24.415	24.411	-0.004
4	Pine	49.5	18.2	5.3	10812	10708	-104	15.649	15.033	-0.617
5	Pine	473.7	58.9	2166.7	1686118	1686123	5	31.087	31.087	0.000
6	Pine	66.2	54.5	12.5	40312	40308	-4	30.886	30.872	-0.014
7	Pine	433.5	211.7	60.3	1339116	1338934	-182	23.794	23.779	-0.015
8	Pine	102.3	34.9	10.4	44383	44370	-13	14.339	14.322	-0.017
9	Pine	485.4	44.4	1474.9	2368876	2369089	213	45.865	45.887	0.022
10	Pine	65.8	59.0	19.2	81386	81374	-12	37.019	36.992	-0.028
11	Pine	425.9	10.8	505.7	627294	627824	529	34.156	34.299	0.143
12	Pine	7.2	17.1	177.9	7063	7060	-4	22.195	22.143	-0.051
13	Pine	357.0	23.0	791.8	615357	615439	82	38.049	38.074	0.026
14	Pine	28.2	5.4	208.8	16336	16332	-4	35.918	35.876	-0.042
15	Pine	196.7	9.8	484.1	325771	329514	3743	30.385	32.120	1.735
16	Pine	2.9	6.0	65.5	1705	1703	-2	20.725	20.613	-0.113
17	Spruce	443.7	67.0	16.6	481034	480940	-94	59.604	59.540	-0.064
18	Spruce	111.6	2.5	142.8	22882	22881	-1	31.978	31.973	-0.005
19	Spruce	4.0	13.3	413.9	9532	9533	2	17.748	17.760	0.012
20	Spruce	16.2	10.1	2.4	3473	3494	20	31.581	32.483	0.902
21	Spruce	301.3	47.4	18.8	266660	266634	-26	55.955	55.925	-0.030
22	Spruce	57.1	2.7	180.4	18108	18106	-1	31.091	31.079	-0.012
23	Spruce	7.4	9.0	333.7	9792	9785	-7	21.379	21.311	-0.068
24	Spruce	28.2	25.9	5.8	10041	10227	185	25.002	27.238	2.236
25	Spruce	1003.4	88.3	3267.9	2422628	2423129	501	46.833	46.884	0.051
26	Spruce	316.2	85.0	24.2	49148	49118	-29	39.811	39.690	-0.121
27	Spruce	27.7	6.9	2.0	3485	3471	-14	47.194	46.174	-1.019
28	Spruce	39.6	3.7	76.2	2336	2335	-2	21.053	20.989	-0.064
29	Spruce	319.2	19.1	728.8	160453	160453	0.4	46.666	46.667	0.001
30	Spruce	138.0	6.2	308.4	36459	36461	2	40.604	40.615	0.011
31	Spruce	8.5	6.2	2.6	1045	1053	8	46.328	48.205	1.877
32	Spruce	15.0	4.2	117.0	1044	1040	-4	19.025	18.742	-0.283
33	Birch	42.3	57.5	736.9	133624	133632	9	21.798	21.804	0.006
34	Birch	22.1	17.8	284.1	51445	51444	-1	23.882	23.879	-0.002
35	Birch	50.2	7.5	214.0	42550	42543	-7	21.765	21.749	-0.016
36	Birch	5.2	3.5	2.8	1978	1976	-2	13.577	13.512	-0.064
37	Birch	57.5	12.2	258.2	43084	43091	7	21.310	21.325	0.015
38	Birch	96.2	5.6	164.0	40739	40733	-6	21.869	21.854	-0.015
39	Birch	87.0	4.7	132.6	41218	41211	-7	22.601	22.583	-0.018
40	Birch	20.9	7.7	2.5	1333	1286	-47	11.500	10.027	-1.473
41	Birch	180.3	61.1	1027.4	513106	513207	102	22.729	22.749	0.020
42	Birch	87.4	16.7	361.8	64555	64554	-1	23.671	23.669	-0.002
43	Birch	73.1	5.1	123.8	14275	14285	10	20.066	20.128	0.062
44	Birch	17.0	10.7	3.4	1358	1357	-1	14.243	14.195	-0.048
45	Birch	65.1	13.4	242.5	54809	54818	9	23.255	23.273	0.018
46	Birch	16.9	9.4	161.1	11971	11969	-2	24.651	24.629	-0.023
47	Birch	50.7	2.9	69.7	5052	5091	38	19.948	20.628	0.681
48	Birch	13.3	6.4	2.1	471	479	8	11.755	12.532	0.777
49	Other	25.8	10.9	114.7	14349	14366	17	17.466	17.555	0.089
50	Other	28.8	2.1	37.5	4587	4577	-10	16.322	16.174	-0.148
51	Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
52	Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
53	Other	27.2	6.6	64.3	11648	11640	-8	13.009	12.972	-0.037
54	Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
55	Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
56	Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
57	Other	125.8	123.9	33.0	98577	98497	-80	50.617	50.397	-0.219
58	Other	4.0	3.0	40.6	475	477	2	18.842	19.133	0.292
59	Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
60	Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
61	Other	22.2	28.0	13.2	6789	6773	-16	40.652	40.168	-0.483
62	Other	6.9	2.7	40.8	257	257	0.1	11.089	11.098	0.009
63	Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
64	Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

NOTE: *coef1* is *xmid* for logistic (Eq.1) or *b2* for Gompertz model (Eq.2); *coef2* is *scal* for logistic or *b3* for Gompertz model

Appendix 10. Management guidelines and standing volumes from MOTTI simulator

Abbreviations:	No. Species	Region	Soil	Site	CL age	PT age	First thinning (T1)			Second thinning (T2)			Third thinning (T3)			Final cut (FC)												
							Vol	R%	L%	Age	Vol	R%	L%	Age	Vol	R%	L%	Age	Vol	R%	L%	Age	Vol	R%	L%			
CL - cleaning of sapling stands (year to apply);	1	Pine	North	mineral	1	-	9	32	142	32	2	98	41	162	28	8	92	55	208	30	41	59	61	176	98	64	36	
	2	Pine	North	mineral	2	-	9	37	117	30	0	100	55	163	29	11	89	78	207	30	44	56	88	177	99	70	30	
	3	Pine	North	mineral	3	-	10	39	119	31	0	100	54	150	28	4	96	74	193	29	29	71	98	220	98	70	30	
PT - Pre-commercial thinning (year to apply);	4	Pine	North	mineral	4	-	12	54	99	32	0	100	69	107	33	0	100	97	138	33	21	79	121	137	98	61	39	
	5	Pine	North	peat	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	105	78	91	-	100
	6	Pine	North	peat	2	-	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	105	75	91	-	100
	7	Pine	North	peat	3	-	18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	115	64	90	-	100
Age - time from regeneration when the operation is applied;	8	Pine	North	peat	4	-	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	135	83	91	-	100
	9	Pine	South	mineral	1	4	11	23	168	30	0	100	31	240	33	25	75	-	-	-	-	-	-	46	343	98	69	31
	10	Pine	South	mineral	2	4	11	30	171	29	13	87	44	249	33	26	74	-	-	-	-	-	-	67	332	98	74	26
Vol - standing volume (m ³ /ha);	11	Pine	South	mineral	3	4	12	29	159	29	4	96	41	232	32	16	84	57	286	34	54	46	69	259	98	76	24	
	12	Pine	South	mineral	4	-	10	36	106	32	0	100	44	111	33	0	100	63	157	33	27	73	77	153	98	69	31	
R% - percentage of removed volume (applied to Vol);	13	Pine	South	peat	1	4	11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	80	69	91	-	100
	14	Pine	South	peat	2	4	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	80	79	92	-	100
L% - percentage of log assortment (applied to removed volume);	15	Pine	South	peat	3	5	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	90	89	94	-	100
	16	Pine	South	peat	4	-	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	105	104	94	-	100
	17	Spruce	North	mineral	1	7	10	45	172	25	16	84	58	224	26	29	71	-	-	-	-	-	-	76	293	98	75	25
	18	Spruce	North	mineral	2	7	10	50	175	25	18	82	67	236	27	35	65	-	-	-	-	-	-	87	287	98	77	23
	19	Spruce	North	mineral	3	7	11	52	135	25	6	94	72	192	28	28	72	-	-	-	-	-	-	92	223	98	72	28
	20	Spruce	North	mineral	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	120	119	88	21	79
P% - percentage of pulpwood assortment (applied to removed volume)	21	Spruce	North	peat	1	7	-	45	121	29	0	100	54	164	28	9	91	64	207	28	44	56	77	214	98	80	20	
	22	Spruce	North	peat	2	7	14	72	107	28	0	100	96	146	27	22	78	-	-	-	-	-	-	120	158	97	64	36
	23	Spruce	North	peat	3	-	-	83	116	26	0	100	100	120	25	2	98	-	-	-	-	-	-	120	121	95	32	68
	24	Spruce	North	peat	4	-	-	72	97	22	0	100	87	110	26	0	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	120	149	96	27	73
	25	Spruce	South	mineral	1	5	9	31	217	33	23	77	42	317	31	50	50	-	-	-	-	-	-	53	373	98	82	18
	26	Spruce	South	mineral	2	5	8	37	257	31	28	72	49	338	30	53	47	-	-	-	-	-	-	64	419	99	81	19
	27	Spruce	South	mineral	3	6	9	35	168	29	15	85	47	242	32	41	59	-	-	-	-	-	-	62	304	99	78	22
	28	Spruce	South	mineral	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	80	159	90	27	73
	29	Spruce	South	peat	1	5	11	48	261	33	22	78	58	357	33	60	40	-	-	-	-	-	-	80	346	99	86	14
	30	Spruce	South	peat	2	5	12	68	205	31	19	81	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	80	222	97	55	45
	31	Spruce	South	peat	3	-	-	58	137	27	0	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	80	197	95	25	75
	32	Spruce	South	peat	4	-	-	53	131	25	0	100	69	192	28	4	96	-	-	-	-	-	-	80	192	97	35	65

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Valentin Ștefan

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